

Gamma-ray spectroscopy of neutron-deficient nuclei in the $A < 120$ mass region

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Declaration

No portion of the work referred to in this thesis has been submitted in support of an application for another degree or qualification at this or any other university or other learning institute.

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Abstract

An experiment has been performed at Legnaro National Laboratory with the purpose of identifying excited states in the very neutron-deficient ^{116}Ba nucleus ($Z = 56$, $N = 60$). The $^{64}\text{Zn}(^{58}\text{Ni},\alpha 2n)$ fusion-evaporation reaction was used with a beam energy of 250 MeV. The prompt γ rays were detected by the Galileo γ -ray spectrometer which was used in conjunction with the Euclides charged-particle detector and the Neutron Wall for the detection of evaporated neutrons. The motivation behind studying ^{116}Ba was to search for excited states and hence determine if this nucleus is octupole deformed. During the search for ^{116}Ba , a new band was identified in ^{115}Xe . Once the new band had been unambiguously assigned to ^{115}Xe , data from an earlier experiment performed at Argonne National Laboratory was used to assist in extending the level scheme for ^{115}Xe . The $^{58}\text{Ni}(^{64}\text{Zn})$ fusion-evaporation reaction was used in that experiment with a beam energy of 265 MeV. The prompt γ rays were detected using the Gammasphere γ -ray spectrometer which was used along with the Microball charged-particle detector. Following the fusion-evaporation reaction, the recoils produced were detected at the focal plane of the Fragment Mass Analyser. Coincidence techniques have been used along with energy, intensity and angular distribution measurements to assist in determining the arrangement of excited states in ^{115}Xe . Following this, quasiparticle alignments and blocking arguments have been used to investigate and assign configurations to each band in ^{115}Xe . The experimental data were compared to theoretical results from Total-Routhian Surface (TRS) calculations and Cranked Shell Model (CSM) calculations with a Wood-Saxon potential. The quasiparticle configurations of the observed bands in ^{115}Xe have been proposed to be based on configurations of particles in the $\nu h_{11/2}$, $\pi h_{11/2}$, $\pi g_{7/2}$ and $\nu g_{7/2}$ orbitals.

Contents

1	Introduction	1
1.1	Motivation for studying neutron-deficient barium nuclei	2
1.2	Previous studies of neutron-deficient barium isotopes	3
1.3	The nucleus of interest	6
2	Theoretical background	9
2.1	Nuclear shell model	9
2.2	Nuclear deformation	13
2.2.1	Quadrupole deformation	14
2.2.2	Octupole deformation	16
2.3	Collective model	18
2.3.1	Vibrational motion	18
2.3.2	Rotational motion	19
2.4	Nilsson model	20
2.5	Pairing and quasiparticles	23
2.6	Cranked shell model	24
2.7	Signature	25
2.8	Components of nuclear angular momentum	26
2.9	Aligned angular momentum and Routhians	27
3	Experimental methods	30
3.1	Nuclear reactions	30

3.1.1	Fusion-evaporation reactions	31
3.1.2	Reaction cross sections	33
3.2	Radiation detection	34
3.2.1	Interactions of gamma rays with matter	34
3.2.2	Interactions of heavy charged particles with matter	37
3.2.3	Semiconductor detectors	39
3.2.4	Scintillator detectors	41
3.2.5	MWPCs	42
3.3	Gamma-ray decay	43
3.3.1	Transition probabilities	44
3.3.2	Angular distributions	45
3.4	Internal conversion	47
3.5	Gamma-ray spectroscopy	48
3.6	Compton suppression	49
4	Experimental apparatus	52
4.1	Gamma-ray spectrometers	52
4.1.1	Galileo	52
4.1.2	Gammasphere	53
4.2	Particle detectors	56
4.2.1	Euclides	56
4.2.2	Microball	59
4.2.3	Neutron Wall	61
4.3	Recoil separators	64
4.3.1	FMA	64
4.4	Experimental details	65
4.4.1	Experiment at Legnaro National Laboratory	65
4.4.2	Experiment at Argonne National Laboratory	66
5	Data analysis	68

5.1	Calibrations	68
5.1.1	Energy calibrations	68
5.1.2	Efficiency calibrations	71
5.2	Doppler correction	73
5.3	Matrices and cubes	74
5.4	Channel selection	76
5.5	Non-detected and misidentified particles	80
5.6	A/q separation in the FMA	82
5.7	Gamma-ray intensity measurements	85
5.8	Angular distribution measurements	86
6	Results	89
6.1	The search for γ -ray transitions in ^{116}Ba	89
6.2	Assigning the γ -ray transitions to a nucleus	99
6.3	Previous studies of neutron-deficient $A < 120$ xenon isotopes	108
6.4	Level scheme for ^{115}Xe	109
6.4.1	Previously published level scheme	109
6.4.2	Level scheme for ^{115}Xe deduced in this work	111
6.4.2.1	Band 1	113
6.4.2.2	Band 2	115
6.4.2.3	Band 3	117
6.4.2.4	Band 4	118
7	Discussion	127
7.1	Total Routhian Surface (TRS) calculations	127
7.2	Cranked Shell Model (CSM) calculations	129
7.3	Aligned angular momenta	133
7.3.1	Aligned angular momenta in neighbouring nuclei	134
7.3.2	Aligned angular momenta in ^{115}Xe	137

8 Conclusion	142
References	145
Appendices	157
A	158
A.1 Measured properties of ^{115}Xe transitions	158
B	160
B.1 TRS deformations	160

Chapter 1

Introduction

The discovery of the atomic nucleus by Ernest Rutherford in 1909 led to the birth of nuclear physics. This area of physics is focussed on developing an understanding of the behaviour and structure of the nucleus, which is known to be a highly-complex, many-body system [1,2]. To date, thousands of nuclei have been identified. The properties of these nuclei depend on the number of protons and neutrons they contain. A number of theoretical nuclear models have been developed which aim to describe the structure and behaviour of nuclei [3–5]. However, due to the complex nature of the nucleus, no model has been fully successful in describing the properties of nuclei.

The majority of known nuclei are unstable and undergo radioactive decay. Often, the decay of the excited states in these nuclei occurs within femtoseconds and, in order to study them, they have to be created using nuclear reactions. Following these reactions, the nuclei can be left in excited states and often decay by releasing energy and angular momentum through the emission of highly-penetrating γ rays. Often, the γ rays are emitted in a cascade and if the lifetime of each decaying state is very short the γ rays are effectively emitted at the same time. These γ rays can be detected and their properties can be studied using a technique called *γ -ray spectroscopy* which has become one of the most widely used techniques for studying nuclear structure. Properties of the γ rays such as their energies, intensities and angular

distributions can be used to determine the properties of the excited states from which they were emitted. The development of detectors, such as the high-purity germanium detector, has assisted in allowing nuclei far from stability to be studied extensively using this technique [6].

The nuclei far from stability become increasingly difficult to observe experimentally as they are produced with small cross sections and nuclei with larger cross sections dominate in the experimental data. A technique known as *channel selection* has become available which allows γ rays which originate from weakly-populated nuclei to be selected from a background of γ rays that are emitted from dominant nuclei. In the present work, the focus is on the neutron-deficient region of the nuclear chart where $A \leq 130$. Of particular interest are the neutron-deficient barium isotopes which are discussed below.

1.1 Motivation for studying neutron-deficient barium nuclei

Neutron-deficient nuclei with $A \leq 130$ lie just above the $Z = 50$ proton gap and in the middle of the $N = 50 - 82$ neutron shell. The nuclei in this mass region are of interest for many reasons. There is the possibility for both protons and neutrons to occupy orbitals from the intruder-parity $h_{11/2}$ subshell. For $A \leq 130$, the Fermi level of the proton lies in the lower orbitals of the $h_{11/2}$ subshell, which favours prolate shapes, while the Fermi level of the neutron lies in the mid-to-high orbitals of the $h_{11/2}$ subshell, which favours oblate shapes. Consequently, these nuclei have opposite shape-driving properties; which can lead to prolate, oblate or triaxial deformation [7]. Orbitals from the positive-parity $d_{5/2}$ and $g_{7/2}$ subshells also lie in close proximity to the Fermi level for both protons and neutrons in this mass region and therefore also play an important role in the structure of these nuclei. As N decreases, into the $A \leq 120$ mass region, it becomes possible for the neutrons to occupy the lower $h_{11/2}$ orbitals, similar to the protons. This could cause an overlap of the proton and neutron wavefunctions and result in the increased possibility of neutron-proton correlations

which can strongly influence the shape of the nucleus.

Octupole deformation is predicted to occur in nuclei with nucleon numbers close to 56 [8,9]. This is one of the main motivations for studying the barium ($Z = 56$) isotopes. Octupole deformation is predicted to occur close to $N = Z = 56$ due to the interactions between orbitals from the $h_{11/2}$ and $d_{5/2}$ subshells which can lead to a difference in angular momentum of $\Delta l = \Delta j = 3$. An experimental signature of octupole deformation is the presence of enhanced E1 transitions and low-lying negative-parity states. The barium isotopes are the only nuclei which are predicted to be octupole deformed and can also be studied in both the neutron-rich and neutron-deficient regions of the nuclear chart. Experimental evidence has been observed which supports the predictions of octupole deformation in some barium isotopes on the neutron-rich region of the nuclear chart; some of which is discussed in Ref. [10–13]. The barium isotopes in this region are predicted to have stable octupole deformation. However, as N decreases toward the neutron-deficient region, the barium isotopes exhibit octupole vibrations. Skalski *et al.* predict that octupole correlations will be maximum in nuclei with $N \approx Z \approx 56$ [8]. This is the region of interest in the present work. Some experimental evidence which is suggestive of octupole deformation has been previously reported in nuclei in the neutron-deficient $A \leq 130$ mass region of interest. These nuclei include $^{112,114,116,117}\text{Xe}$ [14–17] and $^{118,122-125}\text{Ba}$ [18–21].

1.2 Previous studies of neutron-deficient barium isotopes

Heavy-ion fusion-evaporation reactions and γ -ray spectroscopy have been used to populate and study excited states in neutron-deficient barium isotopes with masses as low as $A = 117$. The nucleus of particular interest in this research is the even-even ^{116}Ba ($Z = 56$, $N = 60$) isotope. In the even-even barium isotopes with $122 \leq A \leq 130$, previous studies have identified multiple rotational bands with excited states up to relatively high spins [22–26].

These nuclei can be studied relatively easy using γ -ray spectroscopy, however, as N decreases this technique becomes increasingly difficult to use due to the low production cross sections. As the region of $A \leq 120$ is approached, the compound nuclei in fusion-evaporation reactions become very neutron-deficient themselves therefore the neutron separation energy increases and as a result charged-particle evaporation dominates over neutron evaporation. In the $A \leq 120$ barium isotopes, excited states have been identified in $^{117-120}\text{Ba}$. The yrast band of ^{120}Ba has been observed to over $40 \hbar$ [27]. The ground state band has been observed to spins of $12 \hbar$, at which point it is crossed simultaneously in a so-called forking manner by two aligned two-quasiparticle bands with configurations of $\nu(h_{11/2})^2$ and $\pi(h_{11/2})^2$. The $\pi(h_{11/2})^2$ band is then observed up to spins of $32 \hbar$ whereas the $\nu(h_{11/2})^2$ band is crossed at $18 \hbar$ due to the alignment of another pair of $h_{11/2}$ protons and forms a four-quasiparticle band with the configuration $\nu(h_{11/2})^2 \otimes \pi(h_{11/2})^2$; this four-quasiparticle band is observed up to $42 \hbar$. Two rotational bands have been identified in ^{119}Ba [28]. These bands are based on the $\nu(h_{11/2})$ and $\nu(g_{7/2}d_{5/2})$ orbitals and are observed up to spins of $75/2 \hbar$ (tentatively $79/2 \hbar$) and $79/2 \hbar$ (tentatively $83/2 \hbar$), respectively. No γ -ray transitions were identified to link the two rotational bands. The ground-state band in ^{118}Ba has been observed up to $14 \hbar$ (tentatively $20 \hbar$) [18]. A negative-parity side band has been observed to spins of $13 \hbar$ (tentatively $17 \hbar$) and is possibly based on the configuration of $\pi(h_{11/2}) \otimes \pi(d_{5/2}g_{7/2})$. This negative-parity side band is linked to the ground-state band via three transitions proposed to have E1 character; this is an experimental signature of octupole collectivity.

In the neutron-deficient $A \approx 110 - 120$ region, the $N = Z$ line lies close to the proton dripline; consequently a number of nuclei in this region decay by characteristic α and proton emission which can be exploited using the recoil-decay tagging (RDT) method [29]. RDT enables channel selection and identification for the most neutron-deficient nuclei produced with cross sections as low as several nb. In the RDT method, the recoiling reaction products are directed onto the focal plane of a recoil separator and are implanted into a double-sided silicon strip detector which can subsequently detect the decay of the implanted nucleus. RDT has been used to identify excited states in ^{117}Ba through β -delayed proton emission [30].

Two rotational bands were identified, proposed to be based on the $\nu(h_{11/2})$ and $\nu(d_{5/2})$ configurations; these bands were observed up to $47/2 \hbar$ and $35/2 \hbar$ (tentatively $43/2 \hbar$), respectively. No γ -ray transitions were identified which link the two bands.

In an even-even nucleus, the energy of the $2^+ \rightarrow 0^+$ transition can give an indication of the deformation of the ground-state of the nucleus. This deformation can be obtained using the relationships such as those described in Ref. [31]. Figure 1.1 shows the quadrupole deformation parameter, β_2 , plotted against neutron number for the neutron-deficient even-even barium isotopes with $118 \leq A \leq 130$. The experimental data are compared to theoretical predications from Möller, Nix, Myers and Swiatecki [32] and TRS calculations as described in Ref. [18]. The deformations of the ground states in these nuclei are predicted to increase with decreasing N until ^{118}Ba where the deformation is predicted to be maximum. However, the experimental data implies that the ground-state of ^{118}Ba is less deformed than that of ^{120}Ba .

Figure 1.1: Quadrupole deformation parameter, β_2 , plotted as a function of neutron number for the neutron-deficient even-even barium with $118 \leq A \leq 130$. This figure is taken from Ref. [18] and the experimental data are from references therein.

1.3 The nucleus of interest

The nucleus of interest in this work is ^{116}Ba and the region of the nuclear chart where ^{116}Ba is found is shown in Figure 1.2. The reaction used in this work involved a heavy-ion fusion-evaporation reaction in which the compound nucleus produced was ^{122}Ce . Relative to the compound nucleus, ^{116}Ba belongs to the $\alpha 2n$ evaporation channel; this means that one α particle and two neutrons must be evaporated from the compound nucleus before ^{116}Ba is populated.

One of the main reasons for the interest in ^{116}Ba is the long standing prediction that octupole correlations will be enhanced in nuclei with $N \approx Z \approx 56$ [8]. The identification of excited states in ^{116}Ba will allow this prediction to be further investigated experimentally. The ground-state deformation of ^{116}Ba is predicted to be smaller than that of ^{118}Ba [18]. Therefore, another motivation for studying this nucleus is to investigate how the deforma-

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Figure 1.2: Region of the chart of nuclides near ^{116}Ba . The compound nucleus and the nucleus of interest are labelled. The evaporation channels of each nucleus relative to the compound nucleus are given. This figure is adapted from Ref. [33].

tion of the ground-state compares with that of ^{118}Ba and the theoretical values shown in Figure 1.1. As discussed in Section 1.1, the neutrons and protons in the nuclei within the $A \leq 120$ mass region can both occupy orbitals from the intruder-parity $h_{11/2}$ subshell. The occupation of these orbitals and the influence that possible np correlations have on nuclear structure can be investigated using aligned angular momentum arguments. The alignments of pairs of $h_{11/2}$ protons and $h_{11/2}$ neutrons are predicted, from CSM calculations, to occur at similar rotational frequencies; the exact frequencies are different for each nucleus and depend on a number of factors including the deformation and the configurations of the nucleons. Identifying excited states in lighter barium isotopes will allow the possibility to investigate the effect that an increasing overlap in the proton and neutron wavefunctions would have on the proton and neutron alignments.

The systematic behaviour of the lowest 2^+ states in neutron-deficient even-even barium isotopes can give an approximation of the energy of the lowest 2^+ state in ^{116}Ba . Figure 1.3 shows the energies of the 2^+ states in the even-even barium isotopes with $118 \leq A \leq 130$.

Figure 1.3: Excitation energy of the lowest 2^+ state in the even-even barium isotopes with $118 \leq A \leq 130$. The shaded area represents the energy range in which the lowest excited state in ^{116}Ba is predicted to occur.

The energies of the 2^+ states decrease with decreasing neutron number until ^{120}Ba where a minimum is reached and then the energy increases for ^{118}Ba . If this trend continues then the energy of the first 2^+ state in ^{116}Ba is expected to occur at approximately 220-250 keV.

Chapter 2

Theoretical background

2.1 Nuclear shell model

The nuclear shell model can be used to describe the properties of nuclei by considering the nucleus in terms of independent particles orbiting a central potential. There are several pieces of experimental evidence to support the model. One example is that the separation energies of the nucleons are found to increase with nucleon number until a particular value where a sharp decrease is observed. These discontinuities are observed at specific nucleon numbers which are referred to as the *magic numbers*; N or $Z = 2, 8, 20, 28, 50, 82$ and 126 . Nuclei with magic numbers are found to have spherical shapes.

The nuclear shell model follows a similar concept to the atomic shell model in which electrons are found to occupy specific energy levels. The energy levels in the atom are filled with electrons and the final level includes the valence electrons which are used to determine the atomic properties of the system. The shell model is based on a similar approach and the magic numbers represent the nucleon numbers where the nuclear shells are full. In the atomic case, the electrons move in a potential which is a result of the Coulomb field of the nucleus whereas, in the nucleus, the assumption is that the motion of individual nucleons is governed

by a potential caused by the other nucleons. As a first approximation, the simple harmonic oscillator (SHO) can be used to describe the potential created by the mutual interactions of the nucleons and can be written as,

$$V(r) = -V_0 + \frac{1}{2}m\omega^2r^2. \quad (2.1)$$

The V_0 term is the depth of the potential, m is the mass of the nucleon, ω is the angular frequency of the nucleons and r is the radius of the nucleus. The solution to the three-dimensional Schrödinger equation using the SHO potential gives,

$$E_n = \left(n + \frac{3}{2}\right)\hbar\omega, \quad (2.2)$$

where E_n is the energy of the state, n is the oscillator quantum number and \hbar is the reduced Planck's constant. Using Equation 2.2, equally-spaced energy levels are obtained and when these levels are filled, only three of the nucleon numbers which correspond to the magic numbers are observed. The SHO potential is only sufficient for describing light nuclei where r approaches R , where R is the average radius given by $R = 1.25A^{1/3}$ fm. Therefore, a more realistic potential must be used to adequately describe the properties of heavier nuclei and an appropriate potential is the Wood-Saxon potential which is given by,

$$V(r) = \frac{-V_0}{1 + e^{(r-R)/a}}. \quad (2.3)$$

In this equation, a is the skin thickness of the nucleus. The skin thickness is defined as the distance through which the potential changes from $0.9V_0$ to $0.1V_0$ and is denoted as approximately $4.4a$. The shapes of the SHO potential and the more realistic Wood-Saxon potential are compared in Figure 2.1. For a realistic nuclear potential, the central part should be flat to represent the constant nuclear density. The Wood-Saxon potential is therefore preferred since the bottom of the potential is flat compared with the curved bottom of the SHO. The SHO potential goes to infinity at large distances implying that an infinite amount of energy is required to remove a single nucleon from the nucleus. This is unrepresentative of the short-ranged nature of the nuclear force, whereas, the Wood-Saxon potential tends to zero at large distances (when r tends towards infinity). The edge of the potential must represent

Figure 2.1: Schematic diagram illustrating the different shapes of the simple harmonic oscillator (SHO) potential and Wood-Saxon potential.

the nuclear charge and matter distribution and smoothly fall off to zero. The SHO does not have a sharp enough edge but the Wood-Saxon potential falls off smoothly as r is increased. This confirms that the Wood-Saxon is the more realistic choice of potential.

The energy levels and magic numbers obtained using the Wood-Saxon potential are shown in Figure 2.2. Again, only the first three magic numbers are reproduced and therefore modifications had to be made to the potential. The coupling of the spin and orbital angular momentum of the nucleons must be considered. The so-called spin-orbit term can be added to the potential and is given by,

$$V_{so}(r) \mathbf{l} \cdot \mathbf{s}. \quad (2.4)$$

Nucleons have intrinsic spin s which can either align or anti align with the orbital angular momentum l resulting in two possible values of s ; which are $s = +\frac{1}{2}$ and $s = -\frac{1}{2}$ for aligned and anti-aligned, respectively. Two possible orientations of the total angular momentum j can then be obtained; these are given by $j = l + \frac{1}{2}$ and $j = l - \frac{1}{2}$ for aligned and anti-aligned, respectively. The aligned spin-orbit coupling is favoured and lies lower in energy

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Figure 2.2: Diagram showing the energy levels in the shell model. On the left the energy levels have been calculated using the Wood-Saxon potential only. On the right the spin-orbit term has been added and the splitting of the energy levels is observed. The magic numbers produced in each case are included. This figure is taken from Ref. [3].

than the anti-aligned spin-orbit coupling. This additional spin-orbit term was crucial in the development of the shell model as it resulted in the splitting of the energy levels and lead to the experimentally observed magic numbers being reproduced. The splitting of energy levels due to the introduction of the spin-orbit term is shown in Figure 2.2. Each orbital is labelled by three quantum numbers; these are j , l and n . The latter is the principal quantum number and can be used to count the occurrence of states with a particular value of l . The

degeneracy of each level is $2j + 1$ which is number of m_j substates. These m_j substates have values given by $j, j - 1 \dots -(j - 1), -j$. Orbitals from the same oscillator shells have the same parity π which is determined by $\pi = (-1)^l$. However, the spin-orbit coupling can cause the energy of levels to be lowered resulting in them lying in the subshells below. These are called *intruder states* and have different parity from the other states within the subshell.

2.2 Nuclear deformation

Nuclei with N or Z numbers equal to or near to closed shells tend to have spherical shapes. For these nuclei, the occupation probabilities of the m_j substates, for a given state j , are identical and the total spatial distribution is spherical. However, most nuclei do not lie in the proximity of closed shells and, in fact, deviate from spherical shapes. These nuclei are referred to as *deformed nuclei*. The nonspherical shape arises due to the arrangement of the valence nucleons within an unfilled shell [34]. As the nucleon number is increased beyond a closed shell, the valence nucleons tend to occupy similar m_j substates. This gives an unequal occupation probability of the m_j substates and leads to a nonspherical spatial distribution. The valence nucleons arrange themselves in this way in order to maximise the overlap in the wavefunction and therefore achieve maximum binding energy. The likeliness that the nuclear shape will be deformed is greatest when a subshell is half full. However, as the number of nucleons increase towards the magic numbers, the nuclear shape tends to become spherical.

The radius at any given point on the surface of a deformed nucleus can be described in terms of spherical harmonics, $Y_{\lambda\mu}(\theta, \phi)$ and is given by,

$$R(\theta, \phi) = R_0 \left[1 + \sum_{\lambda, \mu} \alpha_{\lambda\mu} Y_{\lambda\mu}(\theta, \phi) \right]. \quad (2.5)$$

Here, R_0 is the radius of the spherical nucleus with the same volume, $\alpha_{\lambda\mu}$ is the amplitude, λ is the multipole order and μ is the magnetic quantum number which can have values between $-\lambda$ and $+\lambda$. The lowest order deformations are quadrupole ($\lambda = 2$) and octupole ($\lambda = 3$); these are the most prevalent deformations and will be discussed in the following subsections.

2.2.1 Quadrupole deformation

Quadrupole deformation is the most dominant form of deformation to occur in the nucleus. Nuclei with this type of deformation take the form of an ellipsoid shape. The amplitude coefficient, used in Equation 2.5, can be written in terms of the deformation parameters β and γ [35]. The possible values of μ for $\lambda = 2$ are $-2 \leq \mu \leq 2$ and the $\alpha_{\lambda\mu}$ terms can be written as,

$$\alpha_{20} = \beta \cos \gamma; \quad \alpha_{21} = a_{2-1} = 0; \quad \alpha_{22} = a_{2-2} = \beta \sin \gamma. \quad (2.6)$$

The deformation parameter β is used to determine the extent of the quadrupole deformation and the different forms of the ellipsoid shape can be described in terms of the x , y and z axes. For $\beta = 0$, the nucleus is spherical and all axis lengths are equal, $x = y = z$. For $\beta < 0$, one of the axes is smaller than the other two, $x < y = z$, and the nucleus is described as oblate; this shape resembles a flattened sphere. For $\beta > 0$, one of the axes is longer than the other two, $x = y < z$, and the nucleus is described as prolate; this shape resembles an elongated sphere. A schematic illustration of spherical, oblate and prolate shapes is shown in Figure 2.3. Deformed nuclei have a non-zero intrinsic quadrupole moment Q_2 which is related to the β deformation parameter through the following equation.

$$Q_2 = \frac{3}{\sqrt{5}\pi} R_0^2 Z \beta_2 (1 + 0.16\beta_2) \quad (2.7)$$

Figure 2.3: Schematic diagram of the different shapes possible for quadrupole-deformed nuclei. The oblate shape has $\beta < 0$, the spherical shape has $\beta = 0$ and the prolate shape has $\beta > 0$.

Here, R_0 is the mean radius of a spherical nucleus with the same volume and Z is the atomic number. The deformation parameter γ is used to describe triaxiality in deformed nuclei. Triaxiality describes nuclei in which the lengths along each of the axes are unequal, $x \neq y \neq z$. Figure 2.4 includes a schematic diagram which shows how the shape of the nucleus varies with the deformation parameter γ . The nucleus has prolate shapes at $\gamma = 0^\circ$ and $\gamma = -120^\circ$ with $x = y < z$ and $x = z < y$, respectively. The nucleus has oblate shapes at $\gamma = -60^\circ$ and $\gamma = 60^\circ$ with $x < y = z$ and $x = z > y$, respectively. At angles between the given γ values the nuclei are triaxial.

Figure 2.4: Schematic diagram illustrating how the shape of the nucleus changes with the deformation parameter γ in the β - γ plane for $\lambda = 2$. The dashed lines represent three different values of β . The axis directions are given; the x axis and z axis are the rotation and symmetry axes, respectively.

2.2.2 Octupole deformation

Octupole deformation describes a nuclear shape which is axially-symmetric but asymmetric under reflection in a plane orthogonal to the symmetry axis. Such reflection-asymmetric nuclei are often referred to as pear-shaped nuclei; a schematic illustration of this type of nuclear shape is shown in Figure 2.5. The radius at any point on the surface of a reflection-asymmetric nucleus can be determined using Equation 2.5; for octupole deformation $\lambda = 3$ and the values of $\alpha_{\mu\lambda}$ for this λ value are discussed in Ref. [36–38]. Octupole-deformed nuclei have non-zero intrinsic octupole moments Q_3 which can be written in terms of the deformation parameter β_3 as follows [37],

$$Q_3 = \frac{3}{7\pi} ZR_0^2\beta_3(1 + 0.84\beta_2). \quad (2.8)$$

Octupole deformation is a result of the interactions between orbitals which have a difference in angular momentum of $\Delta j = \Delta l = 3$ and lie in close proximity to the Fermi level. The regions in which this can occur involves the interaction of orbitals from an intruder-parity subshell with those from a normal-parity subshell; the orbitals involved in these interactions are $(p_{3/2} \leftrightarrow g_{9/2})$, $(d_{5/2} \leftrightarrow h_{11/2})$, $(f_{7/2} \leftrightarrow i_{13/2})$ and $(g_{9/2} \leftrightarrow j_{15/2})$. These octupole-driving orbitals are found in the regions with N or Z equal to ~ 34 , ~ 56 , ~ 88 and ~ 134 ; these are the so-called *octupole magic numbers*. A schematic diagram of the nuclear single-particle levels is shown in Figure 2.6 where the octupole-driving orbitals and the octupole magic numbers are given. The octupole interactions are stronger when the distance between the interacting

Figure 2.5: A schematic illustration of a octupole-deformed nuclear shape.

Figure 2.6: Single-particle nuclear shell structure indicating the pairs of orbitals which can have $\Delta j = \Delta l = 3$. The spherical magic numbers and octupole magic numbers are given. This figure is reproduced from Ref. [36].

orbitals is smaller and therefore the octupole correlations are expected to be larger in nuclei with $Z \approx 88$ and $N \approx 134$. For reflection-asymmetric nuclei, the proton concentration is higher in the narrow part of the shape. This causes the centre-of-mass and centre-of-charge to separate resulting in the reflection-asymmetric nucleus having a non-zero electric dipole moment. The electric dipole moment is defined as,

$$D = e \frac{ZN}{A} (r_{p,cm} - r_{n,cm}), \quad (2.9)$$

where $r_{p,cm}$ and $r_{n,cm}$ are the centre-of-mass coordinates for protons and neutrons, respectively. For nuclei that are reflection symmetric, the distributions of the protons and neutrons are expected to be equal and the electric dipole moment is zero. However, for nuclei that are reflection asymmetric, the distributions of protons and neutrons are not equal and therefore $r_{p,cm} \neq r_{n,cm}$. The separation of the centre-of-mass and centre-of-charge results in an enhanced electric dipole (E1) moment.

The behaviour of the energy levels in a nucleus can be studied and used to investigate if the nuclear shape could be reflection asymmetric. In even-even nuclei, the experimental signature of possible octupole deformation is the presence of alternating positive- and negative-parity states. In odd-mass and odd-odd nuclei, rotational bands are built on a parity doublet; these bands include states which lie close in energy with same spin and opposite parity. The electromagnetic transition rates can give an indication if a nucleus is reflection asymmetric. Particularly, an experimental signature of octupole deformation is rotational bands linked by enhanced electric dipole (E1) or octupole (E3) transitions. For heavy nuclei the E1 transitions rates are typically found in the range of 10^{-4} to 10^{-7} Weisskopf units (W.u) but for nuclei which exhibit octupole deformation the E1 transition rates are found to be approximately 10^{-2} to 10^{-3} W.u [36]. The E3 γ -ray transitions compete with the much faster E1 transitions, but since they are a few orders of magnitude weaker they are not observed.

2.3 Collective model

The nuclear shell model is useful for describing the properties of spherical and near spherical nuclei by treating the nucleons as independent particles. However, when the number of valence nucleons outside of a closed shell increases the shell model is no longer sufficient in describing properties of nuclei; the collective motion of all nucleons must be considered. Both vibrational and rotational motion are examples of the collective model of the nucleus.

2.3.1 Vibrational motion

The behaviour of the nucleus can be compared to a liquid drop which undergoes time-dependent oscillations around a spherical shape; these oscillations characterise the vibrational motion of the nucleus. The coordinate at any point on the surface of a vibrational oscillation can be determined using Equation 2.5. A quantum of vibrational energy is called a *phonon* and each phonon has an energy of $\hbar\omega$, carries an angular momentum of $\lambda\hbar$ and has parity

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Krane, Introductory Nuclear Physics, Wiley New York 1988.

Figure 2.7: Schematic diagram of the dipole, quadrupole and octupole vibrational modes of the nucleus. The dashed line represents the average spherical shape of the nucleus and the solid line represents the instantaneous nuclear shape. This figure is taken from Ref. [3].

given by $(-1)^\lambda$. The λ term is the multipolarity of the vibrational mode; where $\lambda = 1$ is a dipole vibration, $\lambda = 2$ is a quadrupole vibration, $\lambda = 3$ is a octupole vibration and so on. Figure 2.7 shows a schematic illustration of the dipole, quadrupole and octupole vibrations.

The dipole vibrational mode causes a net displacement in the centre-of-mass which is forbidden by the conservation of momentum and therefore cannot be the result of internal nuclear forces. Therefore, the lowest vibrational mode which occurs in the nucleus is the quadrupole vibrational mode. The first excited state of many even-even nuclei is the $J^\pi = 2^+$ state which is a result of the coupling of the positive-parity quadrupole phonon to the ground state. For two quadrupole phonons, a triplet of states with spins of 0^+ , 2^+ and 4^+ are observed at twice the energy of the single phonon state. For an octupole ($\lambda = 3$) phonon, a $J^\pi = 3^-$ state would be coupled to the ground state.

2.3.2 Rotational motion

Rotational motion is not observed in nuclei with spherical shapes as, quantum mechanically, rotations can not be distinguished on a symmetry axis. Consequently, rotations are only observed in nuclei which are deformed and the rotation occurs around an axis which is perpendicular to the symmetry axis. The quantum-mechanical energy of a rotating nuclear

system can be defined as,

$$E = \frac{\hbar^2}{2\mathcal{J}}I(I + 1), \quad (2.10)$$

where \mathcal{J} is the moment of inertia of the system and I is the total angular momentum. An increase in I would cause the nuclear system to gain rotational energy and in this case the nuclear excited states would form a rotational band. The calculated energies of excited states in rotational bands, predicted using Equation 2.10, deviate from the energies observed in experiment. The difference in the energies can be accounted for by considering the moment of inertia of the rotating deformed nucleus. The moment of inertia is not constant and changes with rotational frequency ω . Therefore, the structure of the nucleus can be considered in two ways; as a rigid body or as a fluid. The moment of inertia of a deformed nucleus described as a rigid body can be defined as,

$$\mathcal{J}_{rigid} = \frac{2}{5}MR_0^2(1 + 0.31\beta), \quad (2.11)$$

where M is the total mass, R_0 is the average radius and β is the deformation parameter. For a deformed nucleus described as a fluid the moment of inertia can be written as,

$$\mathcal{J}_{fluid} = \frac{9}{8\pi}MR_0^2\beta. \quad (2.12)$$

The moment of inertia observed in experimental data, denoted \mathcal{J} is often found to be less than the value of \mathcal{J}_{rigid} and more than the value of \mathcal{J}_{fluid} .

$$\mathcal{J}_{rigid} > \mathcal{J} > \mathcal{J}_{fluid} \quad (2.13)$$

This result implies that the behaviour of a rotating nucleus can be considered as somewhere between a rigid object and a fluid.

2.4 Nilsson model

The Nilsson model is used to describe the properties of individual particles in deformed nuclei. This is a single-particle model with a modified harmonic oscillator potential which

was introduced as the shell model is not sufficient in describing the properties of deformed nuclei. The Hamiltonian for the system can be written as [5],

$$H = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\nabla^2 + \frac{m}{2}\left[\omega_{\perp}^2(x^2 + y^2) + \omega_z^2 z^2\right] - C\mathbf{l} \cdot \mathbf{s} - D(l^2 - \langle l^2 \rangle_N). \quad (2.14)$$

Here, m is the mass of the nucleon and ω_x , ω_y and ω_z are the one-dimensional oscillator frequencies in the x , y and z directions, where $\omega_x = \omega_y = \omega_{\perp}$. The $\mathbf{l} \cdot \mathbf{s}$ term is the spin-orbit force and the l^2 term modifies the potential so that the bottom is flattened therefore resembling the Wood-Saxon potential. The Nilsson model uses non-Cartesian coordinates, therefore, an elongation parameter ε is introduced to account for the deformation of the nucleus such that $\varepsilon > 0$ and $\varepsilon < 0$ correspond to prolate and oblate shapes, respectively. The ε deformation parameter is related to β deformation parameter as follows [5],

$$\varepsilon \approx \frac{3}{2}\sqrt{\frac{5}{4\pi}}\beta. \quad (2.15)$$

The oscillator frequencies can be written in terms of this elongation parameter ε as follows,

$$\begin{aligned} \omega_{\perp} &= \omega_0(\varepsilon)\left(1 + \frac{1}{3}\varepsilon\right) \\ \omega_z &= \omega_0(\varepsilon)\left(1 - \frac{2}{3}\varepsilon\right), \end{aligned} \quad (2.16)$$

where the ω_0 term is the oscillator frequency in a spherical potential. The solutions to Equation 2.14 allow the so-called *Nilsson orbitals* to be obtained. The Nilsson orbitals are characterised by the asymptotic quantum numbers,

$$[Nn_z\Lambda]\Omega^{\pi},$$

where N is the quantum number of the major shell, n_z is the number of nodes in the wave function along z axis, Λ is the component of orbital angular momentum along the symmetry axis, Ω is the projection of the single-particle angular momentum on the symmetry axis and π is the parity of the Nilsson orbital. The total angular momentum on the symmetry axis is K and $K = \Lambda + \Sigma$; where Σ is the projection of spin along the symmetry axis. When there is one single-particle and the nucleus has a symmetrically deformed core $\Omega = K$. For an orbital with a given angular momentum of j , Ω can take half integer values from $\frac{1}{2}$ to j . The values

of Ω are separated by θ where $\sin \theta = \Omega/j$; this results in the splitting of the Nilsson orbitals. The lowest value of Ω lies lowest in energy for prolate shapes and lies highest in energy for oblate shapes.

The deformation of the nucleus affects the Nilsson orbital energies and they change with deformation parameter β ; this is illustrated using Nilsson diagrams, an example of which is shown in Figure 2.8. These diagrams can be used to determine the Nilsson orbitals which are occupied by nucleons. Each Nilsson orbital has a degeneracy of two, this is due to the paired particles which orbit the deformed nuclear core in opposite directions. As the deformation increases, mixing between the states occurs; states with the same K values cannot mix. The same rule follows for states with different parities.

Figure 2.8: Example of a Nilsson diagram for protons in the region between $Z = 50$ and $Z = 82$. The solid lines represent orbitals from the positive-parity subshells and the dot-dash lines represent orbitals from the negative-parity intruder subshell.

2.5 Pairing and quasiparticles

A short-ranged, attractive pairing force exists between like nucleons. This force couples identical nucleons together resulting in the pair having a total angular momentum of zero and spins in opposite directions. The pairing correlations can result in pairs of nucleons being scattered between orbits which can lead to a mixing of states and this creates states with partial occupancies near the Fermi surface. It is then convenient to introduce the concept of *quasiparticles*. Quasiparticles are used to replace particles and holes and represent the probability that a state could be occupied. When pairing is not included there are no states occupied above the Fermi Surface; in this case the Fermi surface λ coincides with the last state which is filled. However, when a pairing is introduced the Fermi surface is no longer distinct and smooths out over a range determined by the pairing parameter Δ , this is illustrated in Figure 2.9. It is then possible for holes below the Fermi surface and particles above it to co-exist [39]. The pairing parameter is defined as,

$$\Delta = G \sum_i U_i V_i, \quad (2.17)$$

where G represents the strength of the pairing force and U_i and V_i are the probability of the quasiparticle state i being unoccupied and occupied, respectively. The quasiparticle energy is given by,

$$E_i = \sqrt{(\varepsilon_i - \lambda)^2 + \Delta^2}, \quad (2.18)$$

where $(\varepsilon_i - \lambda)$ is the excitation energy required to excite one of the nucleons in the last orbit at the Fermi surface, with no pairing included, to one of the higher-lying orbitals ε_i .

The concept of the pairing in nuclei is supported by experimental evidence such as the fact that all even-even nuclei have ground states with $J^\pi = 0^+$. In most even-even nuclei, a pairing gap has been found to exist between the ground state and the first excited state. The energy of this gap is given by 2Δ [35].

Figure 2.9: Schematic diagram showing the effect of pairing on the Fermi surface. The blue areas indicate states that are occupied and the white areas are states which are unoccupied. When no pairing is present the Fermi surface is well defined at the last filled orbital. When pairing is included the Fermi surface smooths out and there is an increased probability of states being partially occupied.

2.6 Cranked shell model

The cranked shell model allows the rotational motion of the nucleus to be considered in terms of both collective and single-particle motion. The model is described as independent particles moving in a rotating potential [40]. It can be used to describe the rotational excitations of deformed nuclei and remains valid for high-spin states. The total Hamiltonian for the cranking model is given by,

$$H^\omega = H - \omega I_x. \quad (2.19)$$

This is the single-particle case where H is the non-rotating single-particle Hamiltonian, ω is the angular frequency about the rotation axis (the x axis) and I_x is the projection of the single-particle angular momentum on the x axis. The eigenvalues of the cranking Hamiltonian are called Routhians, which describe the energy in the rotating frame of reference. When

pairing is included the cranking Hamiltonian can be written as [41],

$$H^\omega = H_{sp} - \Delta(P^+ + P^-) - \lambda\hat{N} - \omega I_x. \quad (2.20)$$

In Equation 2.20, H_{sp} is the single-particle Hamiltonian, Δ is the previously defined pairing parameter, P^+ and P^- are the creation and annihilation operators, respectively, λ is the chemical potential and is used to determine the number of particles in the system \hat{N} . The consideration of pairing in Equation 2.20 allows the construction of quasiparticle diagrams which give the quasiparticle energies as a function of rotational frequency [42, 43]. Quasiparticle diagrams will be discussed in Section 7.2.

2.7 Signature

Signature is a quantum number which is related to the invariance of a system with deformation under a rotation of 180° around the rotation axis. The eigenvalues of the rotation operator, used in deriving the cranking Hamiltonian from the Schrödinger equation, can be written in terms of the signature quantum number α and are given by,

$$r = e^{-i\pi\alpha}. \quad (2.21)$$

The signature is related to the angular momentum I through the following equation [2].

$$\alpha = I \bmod 2. \quad (2.22)$$

Rotational bands are characterised by signature which determines the spin sequence. For even-mass nuclei,

$$r = +1; \alpha = 0; I = 0, 2, 4, 6\dots$$

$$r = -1; \alpha = 1; I = 1, 3, 5, 7\dots$$

and for odd-mass nuclei,

$$r = -i; \alpha = \frac{1}{2}; I = \frac{1}{2}, \frac{5}{2}, \frac{9}{2}\dots$$

$$r = +i; \alpha = -\frac{1}{2}; I = \frac{3}{2}, \frac{7}{2}, \frac{11}{2}\dots$$

Often, a rotational band is divided into two signature partners each of which has a different value of α . The difference in energy between the two signature partners is known as *signature splitting* [42]; this is often expected to change with rotational frequency. One of the signature partners lies lower in energy than the other, this one is called the favoured signature. The phenomenon known as *signature inversion* has been observed in odd-odd nuclei in the mass regions of $A \approx 70$ [44], $A \approx 130$ [45] and $A \approx 160$ [46]. This is when the unfavoured signature lies lower in energy than its favoured signature partner and this occurs until an *inversion frequency* is reached.

2.8 Components of nuclear angular momentum

The total angular momentum \mathbf{I} of a nucleus can be written as,

$$\mathbf{I} = \mathbf{R} + \mathbf{j}, \quad (2.23)$$

where \mathbf{R} is the collective angular momentum due to the rotation of the core and \mathbf{j} is the angular momentum of a single-particle orbiting the core. A schematic diagram of a single-particle orbiting a deformed nuclear core is shown in Figure 2.10 and the different components of angular momentum are labelled. When there is more than one single-particle, \mathbf{j} can be determined using,

$$\mathbf{j} = \sum_i \mathbf{j}_i, \quad (2.24)$$

where j_i is the angular momentum for each individual particle. The total angular momentum along the symmetry axis is given by K . When there is more than one single-particle orbiting the nucleus K can be written as,

$$K = \sum_i \Omega_i, \quad (2.25)$$

where Ω_i is the component of single-particle angular momentum along the symmetry axis, for the nucleons. The I_x component is the aligned angular momentum, i.e the angular momentum which is aligned with the rotation axis.

Figure 2.10: Schematic diagram showing the components of nuclear angular momentum, for a single nucleon orbiting a deformed nucleus.

2.9 Aligned angular momentum and Routhians

The aligned angular momentum I_x of a nucleon is the component of angular momentum that is aligned with the rotation axis. In the ground state of an even-even nucleus all of the nucleons are paired; their angular momenta have opposite directions and equal magnitude and therefore cancel out giving a total angular momentum of zero for the pair. As rotational frequency is increased, Coriolis forces begin to act on the individual nucleons. Eventually, the Coriolis forces will be strong enough to counteract the pairing force and can cause a pair of nucleons to break. The angular momenta of both nucleons from the broken pair align with the rotation axis and add constructively. Therefore, there is a gain in the angular momentum and it is possible for the angular momentum of the pair to change from zero to the sum of their individual angular momenta. When the aligned angular momenta is plotted as a function of rotational frequency a *backbend* or *upbend* would be observed which represents the gain in aligned angular momentum and this occurs at the rotational frequency where the pair is broken. This rotational frequency is referred to as the *alignment frequency*.

According to the Pauli exclusion principle, when the nucleons from the broken pair align with the rotation axis they no longer occupy the same orbital and one must be promoted to another orbital. Often, the next lowest Ω orbital is the preferred choice for the nucleon. If the nucleus has an unpaired nucleon which occupies the next orbital, the nucleon from the broken pair cannot move into that orbital and the orbital is said to be *blocked*. Using this information, blocking arguments can be used along with theoretical predictions to determine possible configurations of nucleons underlying the rotational bands in the nucleus.

The rotational frequency of a transition from $I + 1 \rightarrow I - 1$ can be determined using the following equation [42].

$$\omega(I) = \frac{E(I + 1) - E(I - 1)}{I_x(I + 1) - I_x(I - 1)} \quad (2.26)$$

Here, $E(I \pm 1)$ is the energy of the level with spin $I \pm 1$. The aligned angular momentum I_x is defined as,

$$I_x = \sqrt{I(I + 1) - K^2}, \quad (2.27)$$

where K , as previously defined, is the projection of angular momentum along the symmetry axis and is set equal to the angular momentum of the band head. The energy of the nucleus in the rotating frame of reference is called the *Routhian* and is given by [42],

$$E_x = \frac{1}{2}[E(I + 1) + E(I - 1)] - \omega(I)I_x(I). \quad (2.28)$$

The values for I_x and E_x that would be obtained using Equations 2.27 and 2.28 include both the collective and single-particle components of the nuclear system. The information from the single-particle components can be extracted by subtracting the collective contribution as a reference. The reference will remove the effects of rotation of the core and leave only the energies and spins from the unpaired quasiparticles. The reference-subtracted aligned angular momentum can be written as,

$$i(\omega) = I_x(\omega) - I_{ref}(\omega), \quad (2.29)$$

where,

$$I_{ref} = \frac{1}{\hbar}(J_0\omega + J_1\omega^3). \quad (2.30)$$

I_{ref} is called the reference angular momentum and is characterised by the Harris parameters J_0 and J_1 [42, 47]. The Harris parameters are usually fitted to the ground-state band of the even-even core. As previously mentioned, it is possible for a backbend to be observed when aligned angular momentum is plotted as a function of rotational frequency. Often, the backbend is more clearly observed when the collective rotational effects are subtracted by use of the Harris parameters. The reference-subtracted Routhian can be written as,

$$e = E_x - E_{ref}, \quad (2.31)$$

where,

$$E_{ref} = -\hbar \int I_{ref}(\omega) d\omega. \quad (2.32)$$

For a rotational band, plotting the Routhian against rotational frequency allows characteristics of the signature partners to be observed.

Chapter 3

Experimental methods

3.1 Nuclear reactions

There are several types of nuclear reactions. The reactions used in this work involve the acceleration of heavy-ion beams. In nuclear physics, a heavy ion is often described as a projectile which has $A > 4$. The type of nuclear reaction which occurs when a beam of heavy ions hits a target is dependent on a number of factors, one of which is the impact parameter, b . Figure 3.1 shows a schematic diagram illustrating the possible projectile collisions with a target nucleus. For a large impact parameter, elastic scattering or Coulomb excitation can occur. Elastic scattering describes a process in which kinetic energy is conserved; the product nuclei are the same as the initial nuclei in their ground states. Coulomb excitation is a process in which energy is transferred to the target nucleus from the projectile, and vice versa, through electromagnetic interactions leaving both in an excited state. As the impact parameter decreases, the nuclear-density distributions of the target and projectile nuclei begin to overlap leading to inelastic scattering. This is a process in which the kinetic energy is not conserved and the product nuclei can be left in an excited state. If the impact parameter is small and the heavy-ion beam has sufficient energy to overcome the Coulomb barrier in the target nuclei then fusion of the target and projectile nuclei can occur which can

Figure 3.1: Schematic diagram showing the possible interactions of a projectile nucleus with a target nucleus for different impact parameters, b ; where $b_1 < b_2 < b_3$.

result in the formation of a compound nucleus. This reaction is called a *fusion-evaporation reaction* and is the type of reaction used in this research.

3.1.1 Fusion-evaporation reactions

Heavy-ion fusion-evaporation reactions are often used to populate high-spin states in neutron-deficient nuclei. The projectile nucleus fuses completely with the target nucleus; their energies and angular momenta are shared and an intermediate state is formed. This intermediate state will either undergo fission or will lead to the formation of a compound nucleus. If the system survives fission, the compound nucleus will have no “memory” of how it was formed; regardless of the beam and target nuclei the compound nucleus will always decay in the same way for a specific excitation energy and angular momentum of the compound nucleus. Since the projectile required enough energy to overcome the Coulomb barrier, the compound nucleus will usually have high excitation energy and angular momentum and will initially lose energy and angular momentum through the evaporation of particles. In many cases, charged-particle evaporation is unfavoured due to the presence of the Coulomb barrier so the preferred mode of decay is neutron emission. However, in very neutron-deficient nuclei, the separation energy of the neutron increases and the evaporation of α particles and protons becomes favoured. Proton emission becomes favoured over neutron emission which

Figure 3.2: Diagram illustrating the fusion-evaporation process. It includes the formation of the compound nucleus, the evaporation of charged particles and the decay to the ground state via γ -ray emission. Approximate timescales for each step of the process are included.

increases the N/Z ratio and minimises the proton-neutron asymmetry term in the binding energy equation. Particles will be evaporated until the energy of the system is lower than the separation energy and it is no longer energetically favoured. The nuclear system that remains is known as the *evaporation residue*. Each particle evaporated removes, on average, 8-10 MeV of the excitation energy and only 1-2 \hbar of angular momentum which means that the evaporation residue will still have a large amount of angular momentum. The remaining excitation energy and angular momenta are predominantly lost through the emission of γ rays. The steps in the heavy-ion fusion-evaporation process are shown in Figure 3.2.

The excitation energy of the compound nucleus, E_{ex} , is given by,

$$E_{ex} = E_{cm} + Q_{fusion}, \quad (3.1)$$

where E_{cm} is the energy of the projectile in the centre-of-mass system and Q_{fusion} represents the change in binding energy of the system after the fusion of the beam and target nuclei.

$$Q_{fusion} = c^2(m_p + m_t - m_{cn}) \quad (3.2)$$

Here, m_p , m_t and m_{cn} are the masses of the projectile, target and compound nucleus, respectively. Compound nuclei can be produced with high excitation energies and high angular momentum; typically up to about 60 MeV and 60 \hbar , respectively. The γ -ray emission dominates as the yrast line is approached. The yrast line is a series of states that have the minimum excitation energy for a given angular momentum. In total, the fusion-evaporation process takes approximately 10^{-9} seconds to occur. Fusion-evaporation reactions are one of

the most efficient ways to populate high-spin states in neutron-deficient nuclei with large cross sections.

3.1.2 Reaction cross sections

Cross sections are used to measure the relative probability that a particular reaction will occur. Consider a reaction in which a beam of particles, with an intensity I_b , is incident on a target, with N particles per unit area. If the rate of detection of particles b is R_b then the cross section, σ can be written as,

$$\sigma = \frac{R_b}{I_b N}, \quad (3.3)$$

where σ has the dimension of area per nucleus. The beam intensity I_b usually has units of pnA (6.24×10^9 particles/s⁻¹). The units of σ are barns (where 1 b = 10^{-28} m²). For reaction cross section measurements units of b are relatively large and units of mb or μ b are common.

The number of particles per unit area is determined using,

$$N = \frac{N_A \rho d}{A}, \quad (3.4)$$

where N_A is Avagadro's constant, ρd is the target thickness, usually given in mgcm⁻², and A is the mass number. The rate R_b is given as,

$$R_b = \frac{I}{t}, \quad (3.5)$$

where I is the intensity of the lowest transition in the nucleus being measured and t is the length of the experiment in seconds. This method assumes that all of the decay intensity passes through the lowest transition to the ground state.

3.2 Radiation detection

3.2.1 Interactions of gamma rays with matter

A γ ray can interact with matter via three main processes; photoelectric absorption, Compton scattering, and pair production. The probability for each of these processes occurring depends on a variety of factors such as the energy of the incident γ ray and the atomic number of the material with which the γ ray is interacting.

In the photoelectric absorption process, the total energy of the incident γ ray is transferred to an atomic electron causing it to be ejected from the atom as a photoelectron. The energy of the photoelectron is equal to the energy of the incident γ ray, E_γ , minus the binding energy of the electron, E_b . The energy of the incident γ ray must be higher than the binding energy of the electron. Typically, the electrons in the K-shell have the highest probability of being emitted. This process can only occur with bound electrons since energy and momentum must be conserved. During photoelectric absorption, an ionised atom with an electron vacancy in one of its bound shells, often the K-shell, is created. The vacancy can be filled with an electron from one of the outer shells and during the process a characteristic x ray may also be emitted. A schematic representation of the photoelectric absorption process is shown in Figure 3.3.

Figure 3.3: An illustration of the photoelectric absorption process. The γ ray is incident on a bound electron which is ejected as a photoelectron.

Compton scattering is the process by which the incident γ ray is scattered at an angle θ by a weakly bound electron in the atom. Some of the energy of the incident γ ray is transferred to the electron causing it to be ejected as a recoil electron with energy E_e . The energy of the γ ray is high compared to the electron binding energy so the electron can essentially be considered as free. The scattered photon energy, E'_γ , can be calculated using

$$E'_\gamma = \frac{E_\gamma}{1 + (E_\gamma/m_0c^2)(1 - \cos\theta)}. \quad (3.6)$$

Here, m_0c^2 is the rest-mass energy of the electron. The incident γ ray always retains some of its energy and it can be deflected at any angle between 0° and 180° . The energies of the scattered γ rays observed in a typical spectrum are not discrete and they form the *Compton continuum*. At 180° , the maximum energy is transferred to the electron; this occurs at the end of the Compton continuum, known as the Compton edge. A schematic diagram of the Compton scattering process is shown in Figure 3.4.

Figure 3.4: An illustration of the Compton scattering process. The incident γ ray is deflected at an angle θ by a nearly free electron in the atom, which is released as a recoil electron.

Pair production is the process by which the incident γ ray is completely absorbed in Coulomb field of the nucleus and an electron-positron pair is emitted in its place. The positron usually then annihilates with another electron producing two 511-keV γ rays. For this process to occur, the incident γ ray must have an energy greater than or equal to double the rest-mass energy of the electron ($2m_0c^2 = 1022$ keV). If the energy of the γ ray is greater than 1022 keV then the excess energy is shared as kinetic energy between the electron-positron

pair. A schematic representation of the pair-production process is shown in Figure 3.5.

Figure 3.5: An illustration of the pair-production process. The incident γ ray is converted to an electron and a positron. The positron annihilates with another electron to produce two γ rays which travel in opposite directions to one another.

When a γ ray is incident on matter the probability of which interaction occurs depends on a variety of factors. Figure 3.6 shows the interaction probability of each of the three processes in terms of the mass attenuation coefficients of the incident γ rays. When the energy of the incident γ -ray approaches the binding energy of the K-shell electrons, it becomes possible for these electrons to participate in the photoelectric absorption process. This appears as an increase in the photoelectric absorption interaction probability and is shown as the K edge in Figure 3.6. An absorption edge is also observed for the other electron shells. Photoelectric absorption is dominant for γ rays with energies up to several hundred keV, Compton scattering is dominant for γ rays with energies from several hundred keV up to several MeV and for γ rays with energies above this pair production is dominant.

Figure 3.6: Plot of γ -ray mass attenuation coefficients against γ -ray energy to show the interaction probability for each process. The figure is taken from Ref. [3] and is specifically for lead ($Z=82$); however, the plot is similar for other materials.

3.2.2 Interactions of heavy charged particles with matter

Heavy-charged particles interact with particles in matter via the Coulomb force. The incident particle primarily loses energy as a result of inelastic collisions with electrons and elastic scattering with nuclei in the absorber atoms. The interactions of the charged particle with electrons is more probable as the nuclei of the material occupy less volume in the atom. During the electron collisions, the energy transfer to an electron can cause it to be excited to a higher-lying orbital or can cause it to be removed completely leaving the atom ionised. The amount of energy lost from the charged particle in each electron interaction is generally

small therefore the particle will interact with a large number of electrons and will gradually lose velocity. Throughout these interactions the particle usually has a straight trajectory. As the energy of the incident particle decreases it becomes more probable for it to interact with nuclei within the absorber material. A small amount of energy is usually lost during these interactions however, the incident particle can be scattered changing its direction of travel. Overall, the incident charged particle will lose most of its energy through the electron collisions.

The gradual loss in energy as a charged particle penetrates the absorber material can be described by the *stopping power*, which is the energy loss per unit length, $-dE/dx$. An expression for the stopping power is given by the Bethe-Bloch formula,

$$-\frac{dE}{dx} = \frac{4\pi e^4 z^2}{m_0 v^2} N Z \left[\ln \left(\frac{2m_0 v^2}{I} \right) - \ln \left(1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2} \right) - \frac{v^2}{c^2} \right]. \quad (3.7)$$

Here, e is the electron charge (1.602×10^{-19} C), z is the charge of the particle, v is the velocity of particle, m_0 is the electron rest mass (511 keVc^{-2}), N is number density of absorber, Z is the atomic number of the absorber, and I is average ionization energy of the absorber atoms. The Bethe-Bloch formula begins to fail at low energies as it does not take into account that as the velocity of a positively-charged particle decreases, it will become possible for it to capture an electron. The distance at which the charged particle has lost all of its energy is known as the *range*. The range can be calculated by integrating the stopping power over the energies of the particle, T ,

$$R = \int_T^0 \left(-\frac{dE}{dx} \right)^{-1} dE. \quad (3.8)$$

The range will vary based on a variety of factors; such as the type and energy of the charged particle. The energy loss of the charged particle can be plotted against the range as shown in Figure 3.7. The curve produced in this plot is called the *Bragg curve*. The energy loss of a heavy charged particle increases as the particle loses kinetic energy. The particle begins to pick up electrons as it slows down and this is the reason for the peak that is observed in the spectrum. The peak is known as the *Bragg peak* and it occurs just before the particle comes to rest.

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Figure 3.7: A typical example of the energy loss of a charged particle plotted against the penetration depth of the absorber material. The Bragg curve is observed and the Bragg peak is labelled. This figure is adapted from Ref. [48].

3.2.3 Semiconductor detectors

Semiconductor materials have certain properties which allow them to be used in detectors, these properties are discussed below. Semiconductor detectors are commonly used for the detection of γ rays and charged particles. Electrons in atoms have specific energy levels and when there is a large number of atoms these energy levels can be described as bands. The electrons can occupy the valence band and the conduction band however, they are forbidden to exist in the regions called *band gaps*. The band gap exists between the conduction and valence bands and the size determines the conductivity of a material. In a conductor, there is no band gap and the conduction band is partially occupied allowing electrons to easily move from the valence band to the conduction band. In an insulator, the valence band is full and a relatively large band gap (~ 10 eV) exists meaning that a relatively large amount of energy would be required to excite an electron from the valence to the conduction band. Semiconductors have similar structures to insulators in that the valence band is full. However, for a semiconductor the band gap is much smaller (~ 1 eV). A smaller band gap means that less energy is required to excite an electron into the conduction band. Thermal excitation of an electron leaves a hole in the valence band and results in the production of an electron-hole pair. Impurity materials can be added to the semiconductors to modify their characteristics;

this is called *doping*.

Germanium and silicon are two of the most common types of materials used for radiation detectors. These are both tetravalent elements which can form covalent bonds with their neighbouring atoms. If these materials are doped with an impurity that has five valence electrons then one electron will remain loosely bound after the four covalent bonds are made and this results in negative charges just below the conduction band known as *donor* states. This is an *n-type* semiconductor. If the material is doped with an impurity that has three valence electrons then three covalent bonds are formed and one hole remains, this results in positive charge carriers situated just above the valence band known as *acceptor* states. This is a *p-type* semiconductor.

If the p-type and n-type materials are brought into contact with one another a p-n junction is formed. In this case, the holes can move from the p-type material to recombine with the electrons in the n-type material and vice versa. As a result, the p-side of the junction will become negative and the n-side will become positive creating an electric field which prevents further recombination of electrons and hole states. A region is created which has no free charge carriers called the *depletion region*. Any charge created here is removed by the electric field. The depletion region represents the active area of the detector and its size can be increased to improve the charge collection. The size of the depletion region can be increased by operating the p-n junction in reverse-bias mode in which a positive voltage is applied to the n-type material and a negative voltage is applied to the p-type material. In a semiconductor radiation detector when ionizing radiation enters the depletion region electron-hole pairs are created. The electric field from the reverse-bias p-n junction causes these electrons and holes to experience forces in opposite directions and they are separated from each other. A signal proportional to the energy of the incident ionising radiation can be detected at the electrodes. A schematic diagram of a reverse-bias p-n junction is presented in Figure 3.8. A general expression for thickness of the depletion layer, d is given by,

$$d \cong \left(\frac{2\epsilon V}{eN} \right)^{1/2}. \quad (3.9)$$

Figure 3.8: Illustration of a reverse bias p-n junction.

In this expression, ϵ is the dielectric constant of the material, V is the voltage of the reverse bias, e is the electron charge, and N is the concentration of the dopant. The depletion region in germanium semiconductors is several centimetres wide, making them more efficient in detecting γ rays and x rays. In silicon semiconductors, the depletion region is only a few millimetres wide making them useful for the for detection of charged particles such as α particles and protons.

Germanium detectors are used for γ -ray detection in this work. At room temperature, thermal excitation of electrons can result in a leakage current if the electrons cross the band gap. This results in unwanted background noise therefore the germanium detectors are operated at liquid-nitrogen temperatures (~ 77 K).

3.2.4 Scintillator detectors

In a scintillator detector, incident radiation is converted into visible light. There are two types of scintillator detectors; organic and inorganic. Organic materials are often the preferred choice of scintillator for neutron detection. Examples of organic scintillators are anthracene and stilbene. Inorganic scintillators are commonly used in γ -ray spectroscopy experiments as Compton suppression shields and for charged-particle detection. Examples of inorganic scintillators are NaI(Tl) and BGO.

In organic scintillators, the energy from the incident radiation can be absorbed as it passes

though the material and often results in electrons being excited to a variety of different energy levels. In the process of de-excitation back to the ground state a scintillating photon is emitted. The scintillation mechanism in organic materials can occur in any physical state as it arises from discrete energy levels in single molecules.

The scintillation mechanism for inorganic materials involves the excitation of electrons from the valence band to the conduction band in a crystal lattice. However, in a pure crystal, the de-excitation of an electron back to the valence band while emitting visible light is unlikely. To increase the probability of the emission of visible light impurities are added to the crystal, these are known as *activators*. These activators allow states to exist in the band gap. The interaction of incident radiation in the scintillating crystal can result in the excitation of an electron leaving behind a positive hole in the valence band. The hole can move towards an activator site and ionise it. The electron can then interact with the ionised activator atom, whose states are in the band gap and then de-excite to the valence band, emitting a photon in the process.

The scintillating light produced in both mechanisms is converted into an electronic pulse by a photomultiplier tube (PMT) which is used to determine the energy of the incident radiation.

3.2.5 MWPCs

Multi-wire proportional counters (MWPC) are gas-filled detectors that can be used to determine the position and energy of the recoils produced in nuclear reactions. These detectors rely on the process of *gas multiplication*. Ions and electrons can be produced as a result of incident radiation hitting the gas molecules. The presence of an electric field can prevent recombination and results in the ions and electrons being accelerated in opposite directions towards their respective electrodes. The ions produced have low mobility and do not achieve significant velocity. However, the free electrons can be easily accelerated with increasing electric field and can have a significant amount of energy when colliding with the neutral gas molecules. It is possible for the electron to produce another ion-electron pair. The secondary

electron produced in this collision can then go on to create additional ion-electron pairs with more collisions and this forms a cascade known as the *Townsend avalanche*.

MWPCs consist of two parallel cathode plates with a grid of anode wires situated in between them; each wire is typically 1 or 2 mm apart [49]. The system is enclosed in a container and the gas is inserted. Typically, the noble gases are good candidates for proportional gases however for large gas multiplication factors a quenching agent is required which is often an organic gas [49]. An electric field is created when a negative voltage is applied to the parallel cathode plates; with the high-field regions present at the anode wires. The free electrons formed during ionisation of the gas atoms drift towards the high-field region of the nearest anode wire and are accelerated to produce an avalanche. A large negative pulse is produced on the anode wire in which the avalanche occurs while a small positive pulse is produced on neighbouring wires. This allows the wire closest to the ionizing event to be identified. However, only one co-ordinate is obtained. To obtain the co-ordinate in the other direction additional anode wires can be placed perpendicular to the original ones within the same chamber. This allows position-sensitive information to be obtained.

3.3 Gamma-ray decay

If a nucleus is left in an excited state following a nuclear reaction, it can lose energy and angular momentum through the emission of highly-penetrating γ rays. The energy E_γ of a γ ray emitted from an excited nuclear state is determined by the difference between the energy of the initial state E_i and the energy of the final state E_f . The transition energy is shared between the emitted γ -ray E_γ and the recoil energy of the nucleus E_R however the latter is so small that it is usually neglected. The angular momentum L carried by a photon during the decay from an initial state to a final state must be conserved; this can be written as,

$$\mathbf{L} = \mathbf{I}_i - \mathbf{I}_f, \tag{3.10}$$

where \mathbf{I}_i and \mathbf{I}_f are the angular momenta of the initial state and final state, respectively. A multipole of order L carries away an angular momentum of $L\hbar$; $L = 1$ for a dipole transition, $L = 2$ for a quadrupole transition, $L = 3$ for an octupole transition etc. The possible values of L for a γ ray decaying from a state with spin I_i to a state with spin I_f is governed by the following angular momenta selection rule.

$$|I_i - I_f| \leq L \leq |I_i + I_f| \quad (3.11)$$

The γ -ray transition can be characterised as either an electric transition (E) or a magnetic transition (M). The type of γ radiation depends on the spins and parities of the initial and final states. The parity π of the radiation field is determined using L , as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} \pi(EL) &= (-1)^L \\ \pi(ML) &= (-1)^{L+1} \end{aligned} \quad (3.12)$$

The electric and magnetic multipoles of the same order have opposite parities. For example, when L has even values then the electric transitions will have even parity and the magnetic transitions will have odd parity and vice versa. The parity selection rules are written as,

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta\pi &= \text{no; even electric, odd magnetic radiation} \\ \Delta\pi &= \text{yes; odd electric, even magnetic radiation.} \end{aligned}$$

If there is no change in parity between the initial and final states then the parity of the radiation must be even and if there is a change in parity between the states then the parity of radiation is odd.

3.3.1 Transition probabilities

Often, for a decay from the state with spin I_i to the state with spin I_f , the selection rules provide multiple possible values for the multipole order L of the transition. The probability of which type of transition will occur can be determined by the equation for transition

probabilities $T(\sigma L)$ given by,

$$T(\sigma L) = \frac{2(L+1)}{\varepsilon_0 \hbar L [(2L+1)!!]^2} \left(\frac{\omega}{c}\right)^{2L+1} B(\sigma L), \quad (3.13)$$

where σ is either E for electric transitions or M for magnetic transitions. The $B(\sigma L)$ term is called the reduced transition probability and differs for electric and magnetic transitions as follows [39].

$$B(EL) = e^2 \left(\frac{3R^L}{L+3}\right)^2 \quad B(ML) = 10 \left(\frac{\hbar}{m_p c R}\right)^2 B(EL) \quad (3.14)$$

Equation 3.13 can be used to give the following estimates for low multipole orders of electric and magnetic radiation,

$$\begin{aligned} T(E1) &= 1.0 \times 10^{14} A^{2/3} E\gamma^3 & T(M1) &= 5.6 \times 10^{13} E\gamma^3 \\ T(E2) &= 7.3 \times 10^7 A^{4/3} E\gamma^5 & T(M2) &= 3.5 \times 10^7 A^{2/3} E\gamma^5 \\ T(E3) &= 34 A^2 E\gamma^7 & T(M3) &= 16 A^{4/3} E\gamma^7 \\ T(E4) &= 1.1 \times 10^{-5} A^{8/3} E\gamma^9 & T(M4) &= 4.5 \times 10^{-6} A^2 E\gamma^9, \end{aligned}$$

where T is in s^{-1} and E is in MeV. These are the so-called *Weisskopf estimates*. These estimates, although calculated through a crude approach, give a reasonable comparison to determine which character and multipole order are more probable for a given γ -ray transition. The Weisskopf estimates predict that low multipolarities dominate and also that electric transitions usually dominate over magnetic transitions for a given L .

3.3.2 Angular distributions

The multipolarity of a γ -ray transition can be determined using the angular distribution of the transition. In general, nuclei are randomly oriented and the γ rays emitted from the excited states are isotropic. In this case, the angular distribution of the γ rays would include a mixture of all possible m substates as the intensity of the γ radiation is independent of direction. However, following fusion-evaporation reactions, the recoiling nuclei have angular momenta which are aligned perpendicular to the beam axis. Consequently, the excited states

in these nuclei have spins which are perpendicular to the beam axis resulting in any γ rays emitted from these states having angular distributions. The angular momentum \mathbf{l} of the recoil nuclei produced in fusion-evaporation reactions is given, classically, as

$$\mathbf{l} = \mathbf{r} \times \mathbf{p}, \quad (3.15)$$

where \mathbf{r} is the position of the beam nuclei relative to the target nuclei and \mathbf{p} is the linear momenta of the beam nuclei. The angular distribution depends on the populations of the initial and final m substates. The population of the m substates can be described as a Gaussian distribution centred around $m = 0$ and can be written as [50],

$$P_m(I) = \frac{\exp\left(\frac{-m^2}{2\sigma^2}\right)}{\sum_{m'=-I}^I \exp\left(\frac{-m'^2}{2\sigma^2}\right)} \quad (3.16)$$

where σ is the half width of the Gaussian distribution.

The angular distributions of the γ rays can be described using the following expression.

$$W(\theta) = \sum_k A_k P_k(\cos \theta) \quad (3.17)$$

Here, $W(\theta)$ is the intensity of the γ ray at an angle of θ from the beam direction, A_k is the angular distribution coefficient and $P_k(\cos \theta)$ are Legendre polynomials. The values of k are even numbers, $k \leq 2l$. The A_k values depend on the m substate distribution and play an important part in distinguishing the multipolarity of a given transition [51].

For a pure dipole transition ($\Delta I = 1$) the angular distributions are given by,

$$W(\theta) = A_0 + A_2 P_2(\cos \theta). \quad (3.18)$$

For a stretched quadrupole transition ($\Delta I = 2$) the angular distribution is given by,

$$W(\theta) = A_0 + A_2 P_2(\cos \theta) + A_4 P_4(\cos \theta). \quad (3.19)$$

In Equations 3.18 and 3.19, A_0 represents the total intensity of the γ ray and the Legendre polynomials are as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} P_2(\cos \theta) &= \frac{1}{2}(3 \cos^2 \theta - 1) \\ P_4(\cos \theta) &= \frac{1}{8}(35 \cos^4 \theta - 30 \cos^2 \theta + 3) \end{aligned} \quad (3.20)$$

3.4 Internal conversion

Internal conversion is an electromagnetic process which competes with γ -ray emission. In this process, the electromagnetic fields of an excited nucleus interact with an atomic electron causing it to be ejected from the atom. The energy of the internal conversion electron E_e is given by,

$$E_e = \Delta E - B, \quad (3.21)$$

where ΔE is the difference in energy of the initial state E_i and final state E_f and B is the binding energy of the atomic electron. Following this process the atom is left with a vacancy in one of its shells which is filled with an electron from a higher shell, resulting in the emission of a characteristic x ray along with the conversion electron. The energy of the conversion electron can vary depending on the atomic orbital from which it is emitted. When calculating the probability for γ -ray emission, internal conversion must be considered. The internal conversion coefficient α is introduced and is used to determine the probability that internal conversion will occur relative to γ -ray emission,

$$\alpha = \frac{\Gamma_e}{\Gamma_\gamma}. \quad (3.22)$$

The Γ_e and Γ_γ terms are the probability for de-excitation via internal conversion and γ -ray emission, respectively. The value of α is dependent on a variety of factors such as the atomic number of the nucleus Z , the energy of the γ -ray transition E_γ and the multipolarity of the transition L . Internal conversion is found to be mostly important in heavier nuclei as α increases with Z^3 . As the energy of the γ -ray transitions decrease the value of α is found to increase meaning that internal conversion is more probable in states of a rotational band near the ground state. Also, an increase in multipole order of the γ -ray transitions results in a rapid increase in α . The character of the γ rays can affect α for a given transition; the value is different depending on whether a transition is electric or magnetic. Internal conversion is the main mode of de-excitation in $0^+ \rightarrow 0^+$ transitions where γ -ray decay is forbidden.

3.5 Gamma-ray spectroscopy

Gamma-ray spectroscopy is a technique which can be used to study the excited states of nuclei by measuring the properties of the γ rays that they emit. Such properties include energies, intensities and angular distributions.

The excited states of a nucleus can be arranged into a structure called a *level scheme*. When constructing a level scheme it is helpful to understand the concept of γ -ray coincidences. The excited states of a nucleus can have very short lifetimes (~ 1 fs) and as a result the γ rays emitted from these excited states are often emitted in a cascade. High-purity germanium (HPGe) detectors are often used to detect the γ rays due to their excellent energy resolution. However, they have relatively poor time resolution (~ 100 ns [49]). A time window, typically ~ 150 ns, can be set and all γ rays which are detected in this window are treated as if they were emitted at the same time. These γ rays are said to be *in coincidence*.

An example of a level scheme is shown in Figure 3.9. It can be seen in this example that if this nucleus was populated in an excited state then it could have several ways to decay to the ground state, E_0 . The directions of the arrows indicate the direction, or “paths”, through which the decay may occur. For example, a decay from the excited state with energy E_3

Figure 3.9: Example of a nuclear level scheme. This includes the ground state, labelled E_0 , the excited states, labelled E_1 to E_6 , and the γ -ray transitions decaying from these states, labelled γ_1 to γ_8 . There are two bands shown which are linked via two γ -ray transitions.

to the ground state with energy E_0 could happen via γ_3 , γ_2 and γ_1 (these γ rays are in coincidence) or via γ_3 , γ_4 , γ_5 and γ_1 (these γ rays are also in coincidence). A point to note here is that the decay cannot occur through both γ_2 and γ_4 or γ_5 at the same time, these γ rays are not in coincidence. The transitions obey the Rydberg-Ritz combination principle used to describe spectral lines in atomic physics [52]. This can also be explained using the example in Figure 3.9. The energy of γ_8 , decaying from the excited state E_6 to E_4 , will be the same as the sum of the energies of γ_6 and γ_7 , which also decay from the excited state E_6 to E_4 but through the intermediate state of E_5 . Another example would be the energy of γ_2 , decaying from E_1 to E_2 , will be the sum of the energies of γ_4 and γ_5 . All γ rays emitted in the time window are treated as coincident. They could be from one or more nuclei in the same event which leads to random coincidences within the data. The use of γ -ray coincidences when constructing a level scheme from experimental data will be discussed in Chapter 6.

3.6 Compton suppression

When a γ ray enters the active volume of the detector it can be Compton scattered one or more times as discussed in Section 3.2.1. If the γ ray is scattered out of the detector then only a portion of its energy is deposited into the detector resulting in unwanted background in the γ -ray spectrum. This can be reduced by the introduction of a second detector; an active Compton-suppression shield. This shield is usually a scintillator detector; often bismuth germanate (BGO) is the favoured material because of its high efficiency. The role of this shield is to detect γ rays which scatter out of the detector, therefore it must be large enough to detect γ rays scattered at multiple different angles. A time window is set, usually a few 100 ns, and if two γ rays are detected within the time window in both the detector and the shield then the event will be rejected. However, if a γ ray is Compton scattered by 180° then it will not be detected by the shield.

Compton suppression is used to improve the peak-to-total (P/T) ratio; which is the ratio of the number of counts in a photopeak to the total number of counts in the spectrum.

The effects of Compton suppression can be seen in Figure 3.10. This figure shows both an unsuppressed and Compton suppressed spectrum for ^{60}Co . This nucleus undergoes β^- decay to ^{60}Ni which consequently decays to the ground state emitting two distinct γ rays with energies of 1173 keV and 1332 keV. Usually, the P/T ratio for an unsuppressed spectrum in a germanium detector would be $\sim 20\%$ whereas for a Compton suppressed germanium detector the P/T ratio would usually be $\sim 50\%$ or higher.

Compton suppression of germanium detectors can cause an issue when using high-fold γ -ray coincidence techniques to construct level schemes. It would be possible for independent γ rays which are in coincidence to be detected in the shield and active detector at the same time leading to the non-scattered γ ray in the HPGe detector being rejected. A solution to this problem is to cover the area of the Compton-suppression shield which is facing the target position with a Hevimet collimator. The Hevimet collimator prevents γ rays from directly

Figure 3.10: Spectra showing the γ rays detected in the decay of ^{60}Ni to ground state following β^- decay of ^{60}Co . The spectrum is shown before and after Compton suppression. This figure is taken from Ref. [53].

hitting the Compton-suppression shield therefore reducing the number of false vetoes.

Chapter 4

Experimental apparatus

4.1 Gamma-ray spectrometers

4.1.1 Galileo

The Galileo γ -ray spectrometer [54] consists of 25 single-crystal HPGe detectors which were previously used in the GASP detector array [55]. The germanium crystals are 72 mm in diameter and 80 mm in length. Each of the detectors has a bismuth germanate (BGO) shield for Compton suppression. A lead collimator is used to prevent γ rays from directly hitting the BGO shield. The detectors are arranged in four rings of constant polar angle θ ; there are ten detectors at $\theta = 90^\circ$ and five detectors at $\theta = 119^\circ$, 125° and 152° with respect to the beam axis. The detectors at backward angles and the detectors at 90° are placed 22.5 cm and 25 cm from the target position, respectively. The detectors at 90° are seen in the photograph in Figure 4.1.

Figure 4.1: Photograph of the experimental set up at Legnaro National Laboratory. The HPGe detectors of the Galileo array, which are located at $\theta = 90^\circ$, can be seen along with the Neutron Wall array positioned at forward angles with respect to the beam axis.

4.1.2 Gammasphere

The Gammasphere γ -ray spectrometer [55] consists of 110 single-crystal HPGe detectors arranged around a sphere as shown in Figure 4.2. Each of the HPGe detectors has a hexagonal BGO shield for active Compton suppression. An electronic honeycomb design is used for Gammasphere in which the BGO shield surrounding each detector is separated into six optically isolated segments. Each of these segments is further separated into two parts which are electronically combined. This allows suppression from both adjacent BGO segments if there is no signal in the neighbouring detector. However, if the neighbouring detector is triggered then only the BGO segment closest to the detector is used [56]. Each detector has a BGO backplug for small-angle scattering, which reduces the recorded number of γ rays that have partially deposited energy in the detector then scattered out of the detector, at a small angle. Tungsten alloy (Hevimet) absorbers are used to reduce the number of false vetos

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Figure 4.2: Photographs of Gammasphere located at Argonne National Laboratory [57]. In the photograph on the left, the two hemispheres of Gammasphere are separated and the inside of the target chamber can be seen. The photograph on the right shows the full Gammasphere array arranged around the spherical target chamber.

by the BGO shields. Figure 4.3 shows the components of a Gammasphere escape-suppressed spectrometer. Each germanium detector crystal is of n-type with a diameter of 7.1 cm and length of 8.0 cm and each is ~ 24 cm from the target. The full Gammasphere array gives a solid angle coverage of $\sim 46\%$ of 4π [56].

The HPGe detectors of Gammasphere are arranged in 17 rings of constant polar angle θ . The number of detectors and the polar angles of each ring with respect to the beam axis are given in Table 4.1. The front of each detector is tapered with an opening angle of 7.4° over 2 cm. For the detectors at forward and backward angles with $\theta \leq 38^\circ$ and $\theta \geq 142^\circ$, respectively, Doppler broadening effects tend to be small. For detectors with $50^\circ \leq \theta \leq 130^\circ$, Doppler broadening effects are significant and are largest at $\theta=90^\circ$. At these angles, electrically segmented detectors are used and have an opening angle of 3.7° , compared with the 7.4° for non-segmented detectors. This increases the granularity and reduces the Doppler broadening.

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Figure 4.3: Diagram showing the components of a Compton-suppressed HPGe detector in Gamma-sphere [53]. The germanium-detector crystals, BGO shields and Hevimet shields along with other components are labelled.

Ring	Angle ($^{\circ}$)	No. of detectors	Ring	Angle ($^{\circ}$)	No. of detectors
1	17.27	5	10	99.29	5
2	31.72	5	11	100.81	5
3	37.38	5	12	110.81	10
4	50.07	10	13	121.72	5
5	58.28	5	14	129.93	10
6	69.82	10	15	142.62	5
7	79.19	5	16	148.28	5
8	80.71	5	17	162.72	5
9	90.00	10			

Table 4.1: The 17 rings of Gammasphere with the polar angle θ and the number of detectors at each angle.

4.2 Particle detectors

4.2.1 Euclides

The Euclides detector array [58–60] is used to detect light-charged particles, such as protons and α particles, which have usually been evaporated from compound nuclei following fusion-evaporation reactions. The array consists of 55 ΔE - E Si-telescope detectors arranged around a sphere, as shown in Figure 4.4, and covering a solid angle of $\sim 80\%$ of 4π . The detectors have different shapes in order to achieve the best possible solid angle coverage. There are 20 pentagonal and 20 hexagonal detectors. At forward angles, five of the hexagon detectors are four-fold segmented. Due to reaction kinematics, a larger number of the evaporated particles have trajectories at forward angles and as a result the detectors at forward angles have the highest counting rate which can cause pile up at high beam currents. The segmentation of the detectors at forward angles reduces this problem. The E layers of the telescope detectors are

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Figure 4.4: Photographs of the Euclides charged-particle detector array [61]. The photograph on the left shows Euclides independent of any apparatus. The photograph on the right shows Euclides mounted with Galileo, the Galileo detectors at 90° are observed.

placed behind the ΔE layers in a structure which is self-supporting. The silicon is of n-type and the thickness is ~ 0.15 mm and ~ 1 mm for the ΔE and E layers, respectively. Both layers of each detector have the same area and are separated by a Kapton spacer with a thickness of 0.1 mm. The distance between each neighbouring Si-telescope detector is 0.2 mm. A layer of aluminium foil with a thickness of $12 \mu\text{m}$ is placed in front of each detector as a shield. This aluminium shield is generally too thin to fully stop ions that are scattered from the beam. Additional absorbers in the form of a cylindrical foils are used; these can be easily modified for different experiments. The thickness of the cylindrical foil varies with angle θ ; with the foil being thicker at forward angles than backward angles to account for particle kinematics. During an experiment, Euclides would be located inside the target chamber surrounding the target, with a mean distance of ~ 6.7 cm from the centre of the target to the front face of each detector.

Figure 4.5: Two-dimensional histogram of the energy loss in the ΔE layer plotted against the residual energy in the E layer in one of the Euclides Si-telescopes. The axes are not calibrated so the values are in arbitrary units. The region corresponding to protons and alpha particles are indicated.

The use of Euclides allows channel selection and a kinematic reconstruction of the trajectory of the recoils in γ -ray spectroscopy experiments. However, to achieve this, it is essential to have good particle discrimination for protons and α particles. In Euclides, the ΔE - E method is used by which the energy loss of the incident particle is measured in the ΔE layer and the residual energy is measured in the E layer of the telescope detector. These energies can be plotted in a two dimensional histogram and this can be used to distinguish between protons and α particles, an example is shown in Figure 4.5. The regions of the plot which correspond to protons and α particles are labelled accordingly and it can be seen that the energy loss of the α particles is greater than that of the protons for a given residual energy E . Two dimensional polygonal gates are drawn around the region which corresponds to each type of particle. This is carried out for each of the Euclides detectors individually, and these gates are used when sorting the data to discriminate between the different types of particles.

This provides the possibility for histograms to be created showing only the γ rays detected in coincidence with specific particles in Euclides.

4.2.2 Microball

The Microball [62] is a 4π multi-detector array which allows channel selection to be carried out in γ -ray spectroscopy experiments. It is designed to detect light-charged particles, primarily protons and α particles, which are evaporated from a compound nucleus. It consists of 95 planar CsI(Tl) scintillator detectors. These detectors are arranged in nine rings of constant polar angle, θ , with an angular range of $4^\circ \leq \theta \leq 171^\circ$ relative to the beam axis. A schematic representation of a vertical section of the Microball is shown in Figure 4.6. The Microball has a solid angle coverage of $\sim 96.5\%$ of 4π . To account for the kinematics of the particles, the detector thickness varies as a function of θ : thicker detectors are needed at forward angles

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Figure 4.6: The photograph on the left is the Microball charged-particle detector array inside the target chamber of Gammasphere. The diagram on the right shows a vertical section of the Microball. This shows the nine rings of the Microball; the polar angle, θ , of each ring and how many detectors within each ring are given. Both images are taken from Ref. [62].

to stop the particles with higher kinetic energy. The Microball is designed to fit inside the target chamber of Gammasphere.

In the Microball, the protons and α particles are identified using pulse-shape discrimination (PSD) techniques. The particles can be distinguished by the signal which is recorded when the particle hits the detector. When a Microball event occurs several parameters are recorded. The time of flight between the Microball event and the master trigger, the energy in the first $1 \mu\text{s}$ of the scintillation pulse and the energy recorded for 10 ns after the first $9 \mu\text{s}$ of the scintillation pulse. The latter pulse is used for particle identification (PID). The shape of the pulse recorded in CsI(Tl) detectors depend on the Z value of the incident particle. For an α particle the pulse from the scintillator falls faster with time than for a proton therefore the PID signal will be lower for α particles than it will be for protons of the same initial energy. An illustration of the scintillation pulses for α particles and protons is presented in Figure 4.7.

Figure 4.7: Schematic illustration of the different pulses in a CsI(Tl) scintillator for protons and α particles.

4.2.3 Neutron Wall

The detection of evaporated neutrons in fusion-evaporation reactions can be used to allow channel selection of the very neutron-deficient nuclei which are produced in neutron-evaporation channels. The Neutron Wall detector array [63] is designed to allow such measurements. This array consists of 15 hexagonal units, each of which is separated into three segments. This gives a total of 45 neutron detectors, each of which is connected to a PMT. A photograph of the set-up is shown in Figure 4.8. The detectors are filled with Bicron BC501A liquid scintillator; every hexagonal unit is filled with 6.6 litres. The detectors are arranged in three rings at forward angles with respect to the beam, in total covering a solid angle of $\sim 1\pi$. The face of the each detector is positioned at a distance of ~ 50 cm from the target.

During experiments, both neutrons and γ rays will interact with the detectors in the Neutron Wall. The γ rays interact with the atomic electrons as described in Section 3.2.1. The

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Figure 4.8: Photographs of the Neutron Wall detector array [64]. The photograph on the left shows the back of the detectors in which the segmentation of each hexagonal detector is observed. The photograph on the right shows the Neutron Wall as it would be viewed from the target chamber. Part of the open target chamber is also seen in this photograph.

neutrons will interact with the protons in the liquid scintillator which causes the atoms to become excited. In the process of de-excitation a γ ray is emitted. The detected γ rays are converted to a measurable signal by the PMT. Two pulses are produced by the PMT; the first is the fast component caused by initial interactions of the incident radiation and the second is the slow component caused by interactions of the scattered particles with other atoms in their path to de-excitation. Following the interactions with the neutrons, the protons are slowed down as they move through the scintillator material. They give rise to a larger proportion of the slow component compared to the recoil electrons. This results in a difference in pulse shape which can be used to discriminate between the incident radiation.

For each event in the Neutron Wall detector, the zero crossover time (ZCO) and time-of-flight (TOF) are recorded which can be used for the discrimination between neutrons and

Figure 4.9: Two-dimensional histogram of the time-of-flight (TOF) plotted against zero cross over time (ZCO). The axes are in arbitrary units. This is a plot for the sum of all of the Neutron Wall detectors. The region which corresponds to the neutrons is labelled and there is a polygonal gate drawn around this region.

γ rays. For ZCO methods, the pulse generated by the incident radiation is converted into a bipolar pulse. A bipolar pulse can have positive or negative values; as a result there are points where the pulse can cross zero. The ZCO is independent of the amplitude from the signal and depends on the shape of the pulse. Since the neutron pulse decays slower than the pulse from the γ rays the zero cross over time for both will be different. Therefore, ZCO measurements can be used to discriminate between neutrons and γ rays. Since neutrons have a smaller velocity than γ rays the TOF can also be used for n- γ discrimination. The TOF is recorded as the time between the trigger and the interaction time in the detector. Figure 4.9 shows a two dimensional histogram in which the TOF is plotted against the ZCO. A polygon is drawn around the region which corresponds to the neutrons. This is used as a gate when sorting the data to provide a condition for histograms to be created which show the γ rays detected in coincidence with neutrons.

When using the Neutron Wall array there is a possibility that a neutron will scatter into a neighbouring detector. This can result in one neutron being detected as two separate neutrons. This effect can be handled in the offline analysis in two ways. The first way is to reject neutron signals from two neighbouring detectors in the same event and the second way is to consider the TOF measurement for the detectors which have been hit. The TOF for two neutrons involved in a 2n (2 neutron) event would be approximately the same. However, the TOF for a single neutron that has scattered into a neighbouring detector would be longer. The difference in TOF for both events can be used to identify the scattered neutrons. If the scattered neutron events are eliminated then the background can be reduced in histograms gated on channels which involve the detection of two neutrons.

4.3 Recoil separators

4.3.1 FMA

The Fragment Mass Analyser (FMA) [65, 66] is a recoil mass spectrometer which is used to separate nuclear reaction products from the primary and scattered beam in beam-on-target reactions. The recoils are separated according to their mass to charge state ratio (A/q) at the focal plane. The FMA is 8 m in length and can rotate about the target position to cover angles between -5° and $+45^\circ$ with respect to the beam axis. A photograph of the FMA is shown in Figure 4.10.

A schematic diagram of the set-up of the FMA is shown in Figure 4.11. A combination of electric and magnetic fields are used to separate the reaction products from the beam and guide them towards the focal plane. There are two electric dipoles which are symmetrically placed at either side of a magnetic dipole. The placement of the dipoles allow the position energy dispersion and the angle energy dispersion of the recoils to cancel out leaving only the mass dispersion. The recoils can therefore be separated according to their mass. Two pairs

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Figure 4.10: Photograph of the Fragment Mass Analyser at Argonne National Laboratory [67].

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Figure 4.11: Schematic diagram of the set-up of the Fragment Mass Analyser with each component labelled [66].

of quadrupole magnets are used for focussing of the beam with one pair positioned before the first electric dipole and the other positioned after the second electric dipole. Most of the primary beam is stopped at the first anode in the electric dipole.

At the focal plane the recoils are incident on a parallel-plate gridded-anode avalanche counter (PGAC) [68]. The PGAC is a gas-filled detector, such as those described in Section 3.2.5, that can be used to determine the position of the recoils. In this case the gas used was isobutane. Wire grids are used to detect the electrons in the PGAC and their charge allows the x and y position of the recoils to be determined; the PGAC is position sensitive. This then allows the A/q ratio of the recoils to be determined. The A/q ratio can be used to produce spectra which show only the γ rays detected in coincidence with a specific mass; the nucleus to which the γ rays belong can potentially be identified.

4.4 Experimental details

4.4.1 Experiment at Legnaro National Laboratory

An experiment was carried out specifically to study the very neutron-deficient nucleus ^{116}Ba . The reaction used was $^{64}\text{Zn}(^{58}\text{Ni})$ and the compound nucleus produced was ^{122}Ce . The prompt γ rays were detected using the Galileo detector array located at Legnaro National Laboratory. A 250-MeV beam of ^{58}Ni ions, which was provided by the Tandem accelerator,

was incident upon a ^{64}Zn target with a thickness of 1.0 mgcm^{-2} . At the time of the experiment there were 25 Compton-suppressed HPGe detectors operating which were arranged into four rings of constant polar angle, θ . The number of detectors at each θ are as follows: ten at $\theta=90^\circ$, five at $\theta=119^\circ$, five at $\theta=125^\circ$, and five at $\theta=152^\circ$. The charged particles evaporated from the compound nucleus were detected using the Euclides charged-particle detector. At the time of the experiment there were 49 Euclides detectors operating. The evaporated neutrons were detected by the Neutron Wall; 45 hexagonal detectors were in operation and arranged at forward angles. The use of these detectors allowed channel selection to be achieved. Data were recorded with one of two conditions; (i) two Galileo detectors fired in coincidence with a signal detected in the Neutron Wall for a single neutron event, or (ii) two Galileo detectors fired in coincidence with a signal detected in the Neutron Wall for a two neutron event. This experiment is referred to as the Galileo experiment throughout this thesis.

4.4.2 Experiment at Argonne National Laboratory

An experiment was performed at Argonne National Laboratory in which the $^{58}\text{Ni}(^{64}\text{Zn})$ reaction was used. The resulting compound nucleus was ^{122}Ce . Prompt γ rays were detected using the Gammasphere [55] detector array located at Argonne National Laboratory. A 265-MeV beam of ^{64}Zn ions, which was provided by the Argonne Tandem-Linac Accelerator System (ATLAS), was incident upon two $500\text{-}\mu\text{gcm}^{-2}$ self-supporting ^{58}Ni foils. At the time of the experiment there were 101, of the total 110, Compton suppressed HPGe detectors operating. These were arranged in 16 rings of constant polar angle θ , the number of detectors at each θ are as follows: three at $\theta=31.72^\circ$, five at $\theta=37.38^\circ$, ten at $\theta=50.07^\circ$, five at $\theta=58.28^\circ$, ten at $\theta=69.82^\circ$, five at $\theta=79.19^\circ$, five at $\theta=80.71^\circ$, eight at $\theta=90.00^\circ$, five at $\theta=99.29^\circ$, five at $\theta=100.81^\circ$, ten at $\theta=110.81^\circ$, five at $\theta=121.72^\circ$, ten at $\theta=129.93^\circ$, five at $\theta=142.62^\circ$, five at $\theta=148.28^\circ$, and five at $\theta=162.72^\circ$. The charged particles evaporated from the compound nucleus were detected by the Microball charged-particle detector. This allowed channel selection techniques to be achieved. The recoil reaction products entered the

FMA where they were separated according to their A/q ratio. The recoils were detected at the focal plane of the FMA by the PGAC; allowing the mass of the reaction products to be obtained. Data were recorded with one of two conditions; i) four Gammasphere detectors fired within a 800-ns time window, or ii) three Gammasphere detectors fired within a 800-ns time window but also in coincidence with a signal detected at the PGAC. This experiment is referred to as the Gammasphere experiment throughout this thesis.

Chapter 5

Data analysis

5.1 Calibrations

5.1.1 Energy calibrations

Energy calibrations are carried out to determine the relationship between the energy of an emitted γ ray and the channel number at which the corresponding signal is observed in an ADC. Energy calibrations are usually carried out using radioactive sources for which the energies of the emitted γ rays are well known. The channel number of the centroid of each peak observed in the γ -ray spectrum can be plotted against the known γ -ray energies and a polynomial expression which relates the channel number to energy can be extracted. The polynomial expression can be written as,

$$E = a + b(x) + c(x)^2 + d(x)^3, \quad (5.1)$$

where a is the offset, b is the gain, c and d are related to the gain non-linearity and x is the channel number of the centroid of the peak. If the calibration coefficients are known then the expression can be used to calibrate spectra that include unknown γ rays therefore allowing their energies to be measured.

In the Galileo experiment, two types of signals were recorded in the HPGe detectors; a long trace signal and a short trace signal. For the long trace, the full signal was recorded and this was used when measuring the energies of the γ rays during the data analysis. The short traces were used for timing only and the signals were partly recorded; the time and energy were only recorded when the γ ray hit the detector. The energies from both of the long trace and short trace signals must correspond to one another to ensure there is a time and energy for each signal. To make sure this was the case, the long trace energies were plotted against the short trace energies in a two-dimensional histogram and a polygonal gate was drawn around the diagonal. All events outside this polygon were rejected when sorting the data. This had to be carried out individually for each of the 25 Galileo detectors. An example of one of these two-dimensional histograms for one of the Galileo detectors is shown in Figure 5.1.

Figure 5.1: An example of a two-dimensional histogram with the long trace γ -ray energies plotted against the short trace γ -ray energies for one of the Galileo detectors. The axes are not calibrated and the values are in arbitrary units. A polygonal gate was drawn around the diagonal where the short trace energies and the long trace energies had the same value.

In the Galileo experiment, the radioactive sources that were used for the calibrations were ^{241}Am , ^{133}Ba and ^{152}Eu . Calibration runs were carried out before and after the experiment. The Galileo detectors were not gain matched which means that the peaks which correspond to the same γ -ray transitions are observed at different channel numbers in each of the Galileo detectors. Therefore, energy calibration parameters had to be extracted for each of the 25

Figure 5.2: Plot of residual energy vs γ -ray energy for each of the five polynomial fits. These values are measured from the data in the Gammasphere experiment. Panels (a) to (e) show the polynomials from first order to fifth order, respectively. The red data points in Panel (e) show the best fit. The range on the y -axis is the same for each panel for comparison purposes; it should be noted that this has resulted in some data points not being shown in Panels (a), (b) and (c).

detectors in the Galileo array. For the Gammasphere experiment, the radioactive sources that were used for the calibrations were ^{243}Am , ^{152}Eu and ^{56}Co . There were 101 Gammasphere detectors used in this experiment; these were already gain matched prior to the energy calibration. Therefore, if a γ -ray is detected it would appear at the same channel number regardless of which detector it hits. This means that the γ rays emitted by each calibration source only had to be measured once. For each source in both experiments, the peaks observed in the γ -ray spectrum were measured and the centroids were extracted and were plotted against the known energies of the γ rays emitted from the radioactive sources. Five possible polynomial expressions of first order to fifth order were extracted from the plot. It was necessary to determine which of these polynomial expressions included the parameters which best represented the relationship between the channel number and the γ -ray energy. This was investigated using the *residual energy*; which is the difference between the energy measured and the energy obtained using the polynomial expression. The residual energy was plotted against the γ -ray energy for each of the five polynomials. An example of this is shown Figure 5.2. The polynomial which results in the data points lying closest to the zeroline is the best fit to the data; for this example the best fit is the fifth order polynomial shown in Panel (e) of Figure 5.2.

5.1.2 Efficiency calibrations

The relative intensities of γ rays emitted from excited states become important when constructing level schemes or for determining transition rates or lifetimes. The number of γ rays measured must be corrected for the detection efficiencies. The detection efficiencies can be determined using radioactive sources which have relative intensities that are well known. For the Galileo experiment, the radioactive sources used for the efficiency calibration were ^{241}Am , ^{133}Ba and ^{152}Eu and for the Gammasphere experiment the radioactive sources used for the efficiency calibration were ^{243}Am , ^{152}Eu and ^{56}Co . The centroids and areas were measured for each peak in the γ -ray spectrum and for each of the radioactive sources. To obtain the relative efficiencies the measured areas were divided by the known relative intensity values.

The relative efficiency data were then plotted as a function of γ -ray energy, and were fit with the following function [69].

$$In(\varepsilon) = [(A + Bx + Cx^2)^{-G} + (D + Ey + Fy^2)^{-G}]^{1/G} \quad (5.2)$$

In this equation, ε is the efficiency, $x = \ln(\frac{E_\gamma}{100})$ and $y = \ln(\frac{E_\gamma}{1000})$ where E_γ is the γ -ray energy in keV. The parameters A , B and C are used for the fit in the low-energy region below the

Figure 5.3: The relative detection efficiency plotted against γ -ray energy for both experiments. The spectrum in Panel (a) shows the detection efficiency for the Galileo γ -ray spectrometer. The grey symbols represent ^{241}Am , the black symbols represent ^{133}Ba and the white symbols represent ^{152}Eu . The spectrum in Panel (b) shows the detection efficiency for the Gammasphere γ -ray spectrometer. The grey symbols represent ^{243}Am , the white symbols represent ^{152}Eu and the black symbols represent ^{56}Co .

turn-over point and the parameters D , E and F are used for the fit in the high-energy region. The sharpness of the turn-over region in the efficiency curve is determined by the parameter G . The efficiency curves for the Galileo experiment and Gammasphere experiment are shown in Panels (a) and (b) of Figure 5.3, respectively.

5.2 Doppler correction

Often, following a fusion-evaporation reaction, the evaporation residue will decay in flight and γ rays will be emitted from the moving nuclei. The measured energies of the γ rays are then *Doppler shifted* and to obtain the true value of the γ -ray energy a correction is needed. The measured energy E_m of the γ ray can be written as,

$$E_m = \frac{E_0(1 - \beta^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}}{1 - \beta \cos \theta}, \quad (5.3)$$

where, E_0 is the energy of the γ ray emitted in the rest frame of the nucleus, β is the ratio of the velocity of the recoil nucleus to the speed of light ($\beta = v/c$) and θ is the angle at which the γ ray is detected with respect to the direction of the motion of the nucleus. Usually, it is assumed that the nuclei travel in the direction along the beam axis therefore the angle θ between the detector and the direction of motion will be the same as the polar angle θ of the detector in which it is detected. Using Equation 5.3, it can be concluded that the Doppler shift is minimum at $\theta = 90^\circ$ with respect to the beam axis. However, at $\theta = 90^\circ$, an effect known as *Doppler broadening* is maximised. Doppler broadening occurs when γ rays with the same energy are detected in different parts of the detector. These γ rays have different Doppler shifts and the corresponding peak in the γ -ray spectrum is wider. Doppler broadening is affected by the opening angle of the detector; if the opening angle is wider then the Doppler broadening will be larger.

The discussion in this section so far has been based on the assumption that the recoiling nuclei are travelling in the direction along the beam axis. However, this is not always the case. In fusion-evaporation reactions, the favoured form of decay for a neutron-deficient compound

nucleus is often via the emission of charged particles. The emission of protons and, in particular, α particles can change the direction and velocity of the recoiling nuclei [70, 71]. As a result, the γ -ray energy detected can have different Doppler shifts since the γ rays can be emitted after the direction of the recoil has been changed by the emission of charged particles and is not necessarily travelling in the direction of the beam axis. The momentum and direction of the evaporated particles can be determined using the energy and angular information obtained from the charged-particle detectors. Using this information, and from the conservation of momentum, an event-by-event reconstruction of the trajectory of the recoiling nuclei is possible. Consequently, this can be used to improve the Doppler correction.

For the Galileo experiment, the Doppler correction was measured, as a first estimate, using the FWHM of the peaks in the total spectrum from all detectors summed together. The FWHM in the summed spectrum should be at a minimum when the correct recoil velocity is used. The β value was estimated to be between values of 0.03 and 0.05. Doppler corrections with different recoil velocities between these values were applied to the data and the FWHM was measured for known transitions in different nuclei in the $A \leq 120$ mass region. The value for Doppler correction at which the FWHM is minimum was found to be $\beta = 0.040$. Since the Galileo detectors are located at backward angles with respect to the beam axis the γ -ray peaks were Doppler shifted to lower energy.

5.3 Matrices and cubes

Often, when constructing a level scheme for a given nucleus γ -ray coincidence information is used. However, coincidence techniques cannot be used when using one-dimensional histograms only; a one-dimensional γ -ray spectrum would have γ -ray energy on one axis and number of counts on the other axis. Histograms with dimensions higher than one are required in order to construct a level scheme using coincidence techniques. For a given event, the number of γ rays detected is referred to as the *fold*. An n -fold event can be decomposed

into m -fold subevents; this process is called *unfolding* [72].

$${}^n C_m = \frac{n!}{m!(n-m)!} \quad (5.4)$$

A *matrix* can be constructed using two-fold coincidence data. A matrix is a two-dimensional histogram which has γ -ray energy on both the x and y axes. A *gate* can be set on a particular energy on one axis and can be projected onto the other axis. The γ rays observed in the resulting spectrum are in coincidence with the energy of the gate. For example, if a three-fold ($n = 3$) event is detected which includes $\gamma_1, \gamma_2, \gamma_3$ then this event can be unfolded into three

Figure 5.4: Fold distributions for both experiments. Panels (a) and (b) show the fold distribution from the Galileo experiment on a linear and log scale, respectively. Panels (c) and (d) show the fold distribution from the Gammasphere experiment on a linear and log scale, respectively.

two-fold ($m = 2$) events using Equation 5.4; these are $\gamma_1\gamma_2$, $\gamma_2\gamma_3$ and $\gamma_1\gamma_3$. The matrix would be incremented at $\gamma_1\gamma_2$, $\gamma_1\gamma_3$, $\gamma_2\gamma_3$, $\gamma_2\gamma_1$, $\gamma_3\gamma_1$ and $\gamma_3\gamma_2$. If a gate is set on γ_1 on one axis and projected onto the other axis then the resulting spectrum would show γ_2 and γ_3 since these are coincident transitions. Higher dimensional histograms can also be created. A *cube* is a three-dimensional histogram which has γ -ray energy on the x , y and z axes. Using cubes allows gates to be set on two γ -ray transitions and the resulting spectrum would show the γ rays which are detected in coincidence with both gating transitions.

The acquisition of high-fold coincidence data is possible when using large detector arrays such as Galileo and Gammasphere. The fold distributions for the Galileo experiment and Gammasphere experiment are presented in Figure 5.4. These can be used to calculate the number of unfolded two-fold and three-fold events for each experiment. For the Galileo experiment, the number of unfolded two-fold and three-fold events were 7.36×10^9 and 1.29×10^9 , respectively. For the Gammasphere experiment, the number of unfolded two-fold and three-fold events were 6.34×10^9 and 6.77×10^9 , respectively.

5.4 Channel selection

During fusion-evaporation reactions, many different nuclei can be populated with varying production cross sections. In order to study excited states in the weakly-populated nuclei, their γ rays often have to be separated from a background of more dominant γ rays which have been emitted by strongly-populated nuclei. To do this some sort of *channel selection* is needed. One method in which channel selection can be achieved is by detecting the particles which are evaporated from the compound nucleus. In the present work, the evaporated protons and α particles were detected by Euclides and the Mircoball in the Galileo experiment and Gammasphere experiment, respectively. The evaporated neutrons were only detected in the Galileo experiment, in which case the Neutron Wall was used. The particle-detection efficiencies were determined and are given in Table 5.1 for protons ε_p and α particles ε_α in both experiments and for neutrons ε_n in the Galileo Experiment. The ε_n value is significantly

Table 5.1: Extracted particle-detection efficiencies for the evaporated particles.

	ε_p	ε_α	ε_n
Galileo experiment	28(4)%	24(2)%	$\approx 1.5\%$
Gammasphere experiment	83(1)%	65(2)%	

reduced by the rejection of the neutrons detected in neighbouring detectors, as discussed in Section 4.2.3. Another method in which channel selection can be achieved is by determining the mass-to-charge (A/q) state ratio of the recoils from the fusion-evaporation reactions. The mass of the recoils can be determined using the FMA in the Gammasphere experiment which is used to separate the recoils according to their A/q ratio.

The data from the particle detectors and the FMA can be used to create particle- and mass-gated spectra. These spectra would include only the γ rays that were detected in coincidence with specific evaporated particles or a residue with specific mass, or both. Although no neutron detectors were used in the Gammasphere experiment the selection of channels which involve the evaporation of one or more neutrons can be achieved using the data from the FMA and the Microball together. For example, the detection of 3p plus $A = 118$ in the Gammasphere experiment would be equivalent to the detection of 3pn in the Galileo experiment.

Figure 5.5 shows spectra from matrices which are gated on different evaporation channels in the data from the Galileo experiment. Panel (a) shows the projection of the ungated matrix. A number of γ rays are observed from different highly-populated nuclei in the data; the most intense transitions are from ^{118}Xe from the 4p evaporation channel. Panel (b) shows the projection of the 4p-gated matrix in which the most intense transitions belong to ^{118}Xe . Panel (c) shows the projection of the $\alpha 2p$ -gated matrix in which one sequence of intense transitions belong to ^{116}Xe from the $\alpha 2p$ evaporation channel. However, transitions from ^{115}I from the $\alpha 3p$ evaporation channel are also intense. These transitions are present due to the non-detection of one proton; this will be discussed in the next section. Panel (d) shows

Figure 5.5: Spectra from the Galileo experiment, used to illustrate channel selection with Euclides and the Neutron Wall. Panels (a), (b), (c) and (d) show the projections of the ungated, 4p-gated, α 2p-gated and 3pn-gated matrices, respectively.

the projection of the 3pn-gated matrix in which the most intense transitions belong to ^{118}Cs from the 3pn evaporation channel.

Figure 5.6 shows spectra from matrices which are gated on different evaporated particles and mass using the data from the Gammasphere experiment. Panel (a) shows the projection

of the ungated matrix from the Gammasphere experiment; the most intense transitions are from ^{118}Xe from the 4p evaporation channel, ^{119}Cs from the 3p evaporation channel and ^{116}Xe from the $\alpha 2p$ evaporation channel. Panel (b) shows the projection of the 4p-gated matrix in which the most intense transitions are from ^{118}Xe . Panel (c) shows the projection from the $\alpha 2p$ -gated matrix in which the most intense transitions are from ^{116}Xe . Panel (d) shows the

Figure 5.6: Spectra from the Gammasphere experiment, used to illustrate channel selection with the Microball and Fragment Mass Analyser. Panels (a), (b), (c) and (d) show the projections from the ungated, 4p-gated, $\alpha 2p$ -gated and $A = 119$ -gated matrices, respectively.

projection from the matrix which is gated on the condition of $A = 119$ recoil being detected in the FMA; the most intense transitions observed belong to ^{119}Cs from the 3p evaporation channel.

The spectra presented in this section show that channel selection can be achieved using particle- and mass-gated matrices. However, the channel selection process is not totally unambiguous because the particle-gated spectra can also contain γ rays from channels which were populated by the evaporation of the selected particles plus other particles that have not been detected; this is discussed in the following section.

5.5 Non-detected and misidentified particles

When identifying new γ -ray transitions it is important to take into consideration the possibility of evaporated particles escaping detection or being misidentified. Spectra gated on evaporated particles will always contain γ rays which belong to evaporation channels other than that intended to be selected by the gate. This is illustrated in Figure 5.7. The spectra in this figure are extracted from the 3p-gated cube which is only incremented with the γ rays detected in coincidence with three protons in the Microball charged-particle detector used in the Gammasphere experiment. Panel (a) shows a spectrum gated on the 358- and 496-keV transitions in ^{120}Ba and the coincident γ rays which also belong to ^{120}Ba are labelled. This nucleus is produced via 2p evaporation but is observed in the 3p-gated cube. Often the reason for this would be that a γ ray has been misidentified as a proton by the charged-particle detector. The spectrum in Panel (b) is gated on the 288- and 475-keV transitions in ^{119}Cs and the coincident γ rays which also belong to ^{119}Cs are labelled. This nucleus is produced via 3p evaporation and the transitions are therefore expected to be observed in the 3p-gated cube. The spectrum in Panel (c) is gated on the 338- and 473-keV transitions in ^{118}Xe ; the γ rays labelled in the spectrum are also from ^{118}Xe . This nucleus is produced via 4p evaporation so the observation of these transitions in the 3p-gated cube implies that one of the evaporated protons has not been detected. Panel (d) shows a spectrum gated on the 411- and 516-keV

transitions in ^{115}I ; the γ rays labelled in the spectrum are also from ^{115}I . This nucleus is produced via $\alpha 3p$ evaporation therefore the observation of these transitions in the $3p$ -gated cube suggests that an α particle has not been detected. There were no neutron detectors

Figure 5.7: Spectra from the $3p$ -gated cube from the Gammasphere data gated on transitions in nuclei from the $2p$, $3p$, $4p$ and $\alpha 3p$ evaporation channels. The spectrum in Panel (a) is gated on the 358 - and 496 -keV transitions in ^{120}Ba , the spectrum in Panel (b) is gated on the 288 - and 475 -keV transitions in ^{119}Cs , the spectrum in Panel (c) is gated on the 338 - and 473 -keV transitions in ^{118}Xe and the spectrum in Panel (d) is gated on the 411 - and 516 -keV in ^{115}I .

used in the Gammasphere experiment therefore any particle-gated γ -ray spectra could also contain γ rays from the evaporation of the gating particles plus one or more neutrons.

5.6 A/q separation in the FMA

The FMA, used in the Gammasphere experiment, separates the recoils from the primary beam and disperses them according to their A/q ratio. The recoils are detected by the PGAC at the focal plane of the FMA. Figure 5.8 shows the spectrum obtained from the PGAC; the peaks are labelled with the corresponding A/q values. There are contributions from three different charge states ($q = 26$, $q = 27$ and $q = 28$) and five different masses ($A = 115$, $A = 116$, $A = 117$, $A = 118$, $A = 119$ and $A = 120$) present in the spectrum; the most intense peaks correspond to $A = 118$ and $A = 119$. Using the information from the PGAC spectrum, gates can be set on recoils with specific A/q values and the γ rays that are in coincidence with the recoils can be observed. Examples of such spectra are shown

Figure 5.8: The projection of the PGAC spectrum at the focal plane of the Fragment Mass Analyser. Each section which corresponds to a different A/q ratio has been labelled.

in Figure 5.9. The spectrum in Panel (a) is the projection from the matrix gated on mass $A = 115$. The intense transitions observed in the spectrum are from ^{115}I and ^{119}Cs . The ^{115}I transitions are usually relatively weak compared to transitions from highly-populated nuclei such as ^{118}Xe and ^{119}Cs . The ^{118}Xe transitions are clearly eliminated from the spectrum in Panel (a) however the ^{119}Cs transitions are still observed. The reason for this is that there are overlaps in the A/q peaks in the PGAC spectrum due to charge-state ambiguities [73]. Therefore, recoils which have different mass and charge can have similar A/q values.

$$\frac{A}{q} = \frac{A'}{q+1}, \quad A \neq A'. \quad (5.5)$$

As a result, the FMA is sometimes unable to distinguish between the masses of the recoils. Consequently, the γ -ray spectra will also contain γ rays from other nuclei. Despite this, the ^{115}I transitions are clearly observed. The spectrum in Panel (b) shows the projection from the matrix gated on $A = 116$ and the most intense transitions are from ^{116}Xe . Panel (c) shows the projection from the matrix gated on $A = 117$. The most intense transitions in this spectrum are from ^{118}Xe and ^{116}Xe however, unlike the other spectra, the ^{117}Xe transitions can be clearly identified. Panel (d) shows the projection from the matrix gated on $A = 118$; the most intense transitions are from ^{118}Xe . Panel (e) shows the projection from the matrix gated on $A = 119$; the most intense transitions are from ^{119}Cs . The spectrum in Panel (f) shows the projection from the matrix gated on $A = 120$. The most intense transitions are from ^{119}Cs , however transitions from ^{120}Ba can be clearly observed. The spectra discussed here clearly illustrate the separation of different masses.

The transport efficiency of the FMA is different for different recoiling nuclei depending on the particles that are evaporated from the compound nucleus. The transport efficiency was measured using the ratio of intensities of transitions in an ungated $\gamma\gamma$ matrix and a recoil-gated $\gamma\gamma$ matrix. For recoils from which only neutrons and protons were evaporated the transport efficiency was measured to be around 4%. However, if an α particle was evaporated the efficiency was found to be significantly less with a value of around 1%.

Figure 5.9: Spectra gated on different masses detected by the PGAC at the focal plane of the FMA in the Gammasphere experiment. Panels (a), (b), (c), (d), (e) and (f) show spectra gated on $A = 115, 116, 117, 118, 119$ and 120 , respectively. The γ rays present in the spectra are labelled with different colours to distinguish the nucleus from which they are emitted.

5.7 Gamma-ray intensity measurements

When constructing a level scheme the intensities of the γ rays emitted from the excited states are important. High-spin states are usually populated in fusion-evaporation reactions and as these states decay the intensity is collected by the lower-lying states. As a result the intensity of the γ rays emitted from excited states often increase as the ground state is approached. This means that when performing γ -ray intensity measurements using gated spectra the gates must be set on γ -ray transitions below the transitions of interest; this will ensure that all feeding which results in the increased population of the excited states is considered.

As already discussed, the γ -ray detectors can have different detection efficiencies and they vary as a function of γ -ray energy. It is important to consider these efficiencies when measuring γ -ray intensities. Internal conversion competes with γ -ray decay and should also be considered when carrying out γ -ray intensity measurements. The total transition intensity of the γ ray I_T can be written as the area N_γ of the peak measured in the spectrum with corrections for relative detection efficiency ε and internal conversion as follows.

$$I_T = N_\gamma \frac{(1 + \alpha)}{\varepsilon} \quad (5.6)$$

In this equation, α is the internal conversion coefficient for the transition in question. The value of α can be obtained from the online internal conversion coefficient calculator BRICC [74] if the γ -ray energy and multipolarity of the transition are known. The ε value is taken from the efficiency calibration. Equation 5.6 allows the intensities of γ rays which are measured in one-dimensional histograms to be determined. However, if two- or three-dimensional histograms are used the equation has to be modified to account for the efficiency and internal conversion coefficients for the γ -ray energies at which any gates have been set. Taking this into account, the intensity of a γ ray extracted from a matrix can be written as,

$$I_T = N_{\gamma\gamma} \frac{(1 + \alpha)}{\varepsilon} \frac{(1 + \alpha_{gate})}{\varepsilon_{gate}}, \quad (5.7)$$

where $N_{\gamma\gamma}$ is the area of the peak measured in the gated matrix and the additional terms, α_{gate} and ε_{gate} , are the internal conversion coefficient and efficiency of the gated energy,

respectively. If more than one gate is used then the internal conversion coefficient and efficiency of each gate must be included. When carrying out γ -ray intensity measurements using Equation 5.7, the angular distribution coefficient, $W(\theta)$ and the branching ratio of the gating transition should be taken into consideration. However, in this case both are ~ 1 .

5.8 Angular distribution measurements

Angular distributions were discussed in Section 3.3.2. The angular distributions of γ rays can be determined by measuring the intensities of the γ -ray transitions at different values of polar angle θ . If the nuclei are oriented, which is usually the case following fusion-evaporation reactions, the angular distributions are dependent on the multiplicities of the γ -ray transi-

Figure 5.10: Schematic illustration of the angular distributions of γ rays for a stretched-dipole and stretched-quadrupole transition. The stretched-dipole transitions are distributed at $\theta \approx 90^\circ$ and the stretched-quadrupole transitions are distributed at forward and backward angles at $\theta \approx 40^\circ$ and $\theta \approx 140^\circ$, respectively, with respect to the beam axis z .

tions. Stretched-dipole transitions are more intense at $\theta \approx 90^\circ$ with respect to the beam axis whereas stretched-quadrupole transitions are more intense for forward and backward angles with $\theta \approx 40^\circ$ and $\theta \approx 140^\circ$, respectively. A schematic illustration of these distributions is shown in Figure 5.10. The ratio of intensities of a γ ray detected at forward and backward angles (I_{FB}) and at $\sim 90^\circ$ (I_{90}) can be used to help infer the multipolarity of the transition.

$$R_\theta = \frac{I_{\text{FB}}}{I_{90}} \quad (5.8)$$

The R_θ value is < 1 for stretched-dipole transitions and > 1 for stretched-quadrupole transitions.

The angular distributions were measured using the data from the Gammasphere experiment. Two $\gamma\gamma$ matrices were created, one of which had γ -ray energy detected at $\theta \approx 90^\circ$ on the

Figure 5.11: The detection efficiencies of the Gammasphere detectors at different angles of θ . The spectrum in Panel (a) shows the detection efficiency of the detectors positioned at $\theta \approx 90^\circ$ and the spectrum in Panel (b) shows the detection efficiency of the detectors positioned at $\theta \approx 40^\circ$ and $\theta \approx 140^\circ$.

y -axis and the other had γ -ray energy detected at forward and backward angles with $\theta \approx 40^\circ$ and $\theta \approx 140^\circ$, respectively, on the y -axis. Both matrices had γ -ray energy detected at any angle of θ on the x -axis. Gates were set on the x -axis of both matrices and projected onto the y -axes where the areas and energies of the coincident γ -rays were measured. To obtain the intensities of the γ rays, the areas have to be corrected for efficiency. The efficiency calibration discussed in Section 5.1.2 was not sufficient as it contains all detectors in the Gammasphere array. However, there are only 30 detectors at $\theta \approx 90^\circ$ and a total of 40 detectors at $\theta \approx 40^\circ$ and $\theta \approx 140^\circ$. Therefore, efficiency calibration had to be carried out to obtain two separate efficiency curves one which included only the detectors at $\theta \approx 90^\circ$ and the other included detectors at $\theta \approx 40^\circ$ and $\theta \approx 140^\circ$. These curves are presented in Figure 5.11; the efficiency values of the detectors at $\theta \approx 40^\circ$ and $\theta \approx 140^\circ$ are smaller than the efficiency values at $\theta \approx 90^\circ$. Once the intensities of the γ rays were measured the R_θ values were obtained using Equation 5.8.

Known transitions in neighbouring nuclei were measured to calibrate the R_θ values for stretched-dipole and stretched-quadrupole transitions. The R_θ value for a stretched-dipole transition was found to be ~ 0.7 and for a stretched-quadrupole transition was found to be ~ 1.4 . The character of the emitted radiation can not be determined by angular distribution measurements however the spins and parities can be inferred using the angular distribution and can be compared to bands in neighbouring nuclei.

Chapter 6

Results

6.1 The search for γ -ray transitions in ^{116}Ba

To date, no excited states have been reported in ^{116}Ba and the primary focus of this work was to search for γ -ray transitions emitted from this nucleus. The energy of the first excited state in ^{116}Ba is expected to be approximately in the energy range of 220-250 keV, as discussed in Section 1.3. In the reaction used in this work, one α particle and two neutrons must be evaporated from the compound nucleus for ^{116}Ba to be populated. Since the favoured form of decay for a neutron-deficient compound nucleus is often through the emission of charged particles, and not neutron emission, ^{116}Ba is produced with low cross sections. As a result, in the total projection spectrum, the ^{116}Ba transitions are likely to be buried in amongst transitions from more dominant evaporation channels. However, as discussed in Section 5.4, particle-gated matrices can be created which allow channel selection techniques to be used.

For the purpose of the search for transitions in ^{116}Ba , the data from the Galileo experiment was primarily used. A number of nuclei were populated in that experiment and amongst the strongly-populated nuclei were ^{118}Xe (4p evaporation), ^{119}Cs (3p), ^{116}Xe (α 2p) and ^{115}I (α 3p). Transitions from these nuclei tend to dominate in most of the spectra produced us-

ing this data. Prior to searching for ^{116}Ba ($\alpha 2n$), the data were analysed to investigate if transitions from other nuclei, which are populated via the evaporation of $2n$, are observed. Transitions from ^{118}Ba (α or $2p2n$) and ^{117}Cs (αp or $3p2n$) are observed in the $2p2n$ -gated matrix produced from the Galileo data and are shown in Figure 6.1. The spectrum in Panel (a) is gated on the 360-keV transition in ^{118}Ba and the coincident transitions observed in this spectrum are from ^{118}Ba . The spectrum in Panel (b) is gated on the 495-keV transition in ^{117}Cs ; although coincident transitions in ^{117}Cs are observed this spectrum is also contaminated with transitions from ^{118}Ba . Excited states have been previously identified in ^{112}Xe ($2\alpha 2n$) [14] and the data were analysed to determine if these transitions were present. However, transitions from this nucleus could not be observed. Although there are very few evaporation channels containing $2n$ evaporation in the data, the observation of ^{118}Ba and

Figure 6.1: Spectra from the $2p2n$ -gated matrix from the Galileo experiment. The spectrum in Panel (a) is gated on the 360-keV transition from ^{118}Ba and the spectrum in Panel (b) is gated on the 495-keV transition in ^{117}Cs . The transitions from ^{118}Ba and ^{117}Cs are labelled in black and red, respectively.

^{117}Cs in the 2p2n-gated matrix indicates that it is possible to observe nuclei produced in these evaporation channels.

Since the nucleus of interest is ^{116}Ba , the data were analysed to investigate if transitions were observed in the neighbouring barium isotopes. Matrices gated on evaporated particles were analysed and gates were set on known transitions in $^{120,119,118,117}\text{Ba}$. However, only transitions in ^{118}Ba (α or 2p2n) could be clearly identified. Transitions from $^{120,119,117}\text{Ba}$ could not be clearly identified in any of the matrices gated on evaporated particles however they were likely present but buried in the background of transitions from nuclei produced with larger

Figure 6.2: Spectra from the particle-ungated cube from the Gaileo experiment. The spectrum in Panel (a) is double-gated on the 185- and 358-keV transitions in ^{120}Ba , the spectrum in Panel (b) is double-gated on the 207- and 364-keV transitions in ^{119}Ba and the spectrum in Panel (c) is double-gated on the 360- and 489-keV transitions in ^{118}Ba .

cross sections. For example, ^{120}Ba is produced via the evaporation of 2p however the 2p-gated matrix is highly contaminated with transitions from ^{118}Xe (4p) and ^{119}Cs (3p). A cube was sorted using the Galileo data which had no particle gates. In this cube, the transitions in $^{120,119,118}\text{Ba}$ were observed and are shown in the double-gated spectra in Figure 6.2. The spectrum in Panel (a) is double-gated on the 185- and 358-keV transitions from ^{120}Ba ; the coincident transitions in ^{120}Ba are labelled. The spectrum in Panel (b) is double-gated on the 207- and 364-keV transitions in ^{119}Ba ; the coincident transitions in ^{119}Ba are labelled. The spectrum in Panel (c) is double-gated on the 360- and 489-keV transitions in ^{118}Ba ; the coincident transitions in ^{118}Ba are labelled. Transitions from ^{117}Ba could not be observed in the cube sorted from this data.

The cross section of ^{118}Ba was measured to assist in determining an upper limit on the cross section of ^{116}Ba ; this was carried out using the method discussed in Section 3.1.2. The intensity of the 194-keV transition ($2^+ \rightarrow 0^+$) in ^{118}Ba was measured in the 2p2n-gated matrix in which a gate was set on the 360-keV transition ($4^+ \rightarrow 2^+$). The intensity was corrected for the detection efficiency of the γ rays in Galileo, the detection efficiency of the particle gates in Euclides and the Neutron Wall and internal conversion. The cross section of ^{118}Ba was measured to be $76.4 \mu\text{b}$. Following this, the upper limit of the cross section of ^{116}Ba was estimated to be $\sim 35 \mu\text{b}$.

The data from the Galileo experiment was sorted to create an $\alpha 2\text{n}$ -gated matrix. The projection of this matrix is shown in Panel (a) of Figure 6.3. As previously discussed in Section 5.5, the particle-gated spectra are often contaminated with γ rays emitted from nuclei from other evaporation channels. This is observed in the projection where the most intense transitions are from ^{115}Xe produced in the $\alpha 2\text{pn}$ evaporation channel; transitions in ^{116}Xe ($\alpha 2\text{p}$) and ^{116}Cs (αpn) are also identified in the projection. However, there were also some intense γ -ray transitions present which have not been previously reported in any neighbouring nuclei. These transitions are labelled in red in the projection and have energies of 210, 543, 603 and 618 keV. There is a γ -ray transition in ^{116}Xe with an energy of 616 keV which decays from $6^+ \rightarrow 4^+$ and contributions from this transition will be present in the peak that is observed

Figure 6.3: Spectra from the $\alpha 2n$ -gated matrix from the Galileo experiment. The spectrum in Panel (a) is the projection. The intense peaks are labelled with the γ -ray energies and the nuclei to which they belong and the unidentified transitions are labelled in red. The spectrum in Panel (b) is gated on the 210-keV transition.

at 618 keV in the projection. However, since the peak is more intense than the 394- and 524-keV transitions from ^{116}Xe , which decay from $2^+ \rightarrow 0^+$ and $4^+ \rightarrow 2^+$, respectively, it is unlikely to be only due to that one transition. A gate was set on the 210-keV transition and the resulting spectrum is shown in Panel (b) of Figure 6.3. The transitions from the other nuclei are no longer present however the 543-, 603- and 618-keV transitions are still observed, showing that they are coincident with the 210-keV transition. Two additional transitions are also seen which have energies of 638 keV and 659 keV. This spectrum only shows that the unidentified transitions are in coincidence with the 210-keV transition and in order to investigate if the unidentified transitions were in coincidence with each other, the ungated cube from the Galileo experiment was used. Some spectra from this cube are shown in Figure 6.4. The spectrum in Panel (a) is double-gated on 210 and 603 keV, the spectrum in Panel (b) is

Figure 6.4: Triple coincidence spectra from the ungated cube from the Galileo experiment. The spectrum in Panel (a) is double-gated on 210 and 603 keV, the spectrum in Panel (b) is double-gated on 543 and 603 keV and the spectrum in Panel (c) is double-gated on 603 and 638 keV.

double-gated on 543 and 603 keV and the spectrum in Panel (c) is double-gated on 603 and 638 keV. The use of the cube concluded that unidentified transitions are coincident and that there is another transition present at 720 keV. The 720-keV transition looks like a doublet especially in Panel (c) and the FWHM of this peak in Panel (a) is wider than that of the other transitions.

The fact that transitions are present in the $\alpha 2n$ -gated matrix does not necessarily mean that they are emitted by the nucleus from the $\alpha 2n$ evaporation channel. The transitions in coincidence with the 210-keV transition are also observed in the projection spectra of the α -, αp -, $\alpha 2p$ -, αn -, αpn - and $\alpha 2pn$ -gated matrices. The 210-keV transition was also observed in

other matrices which were not gated on an α particle. However, the other transitions were difficult to identify as they are very weak and buried in a background of more intense γ rays both in the projection of these matrices and in spectra gated on the 210-keV transition. Figures 6.5 and 6.6 show spectra from different particle-gated matrices that are gated on the 210-keV transition. In the spectra from the α -, αp - and $\alpha 2p$ -gated matrices, the most intense peaks correspond to transitions from highly-populated nuclei in the α particle evaporation channels; these are ^{115}I produced by $\alpha 3p$ evaporation and ^{116}Xe produced by $\alpha 2p$ evaporation. However, in the spectra from matrices which are gated on an evaporated neutron, the αn , αpn and $\alpha 2pn$ -gated matrices, the transitions from ^{115}I and ^{116}Xe are significantly reduced or

Figure 6.5: Spectra from particle-gated matrices extracted from the Galileo experiment. Panels (a), (b) and (c) show spectra gated on the 210-keV transition from α -, αp - and $\alpha 2p$ -gated matrices, respectively. The unidentified transitions in this work are labelled in red.

no longer observed, as expected. The spectra from these matrices also show the transition at 720 keV. The unidentified transitions in coincidence with the 210-keV transition are clearly observed in the matrices gated on an evaporated neutron. This suggests that the transitions are from a reaction channel which involves the evaporation of at least one neutron. The methods used in assigning the transitions to a particular nucleus are discussed in the next section.

The data from the Gammasphere experiment were also examined to investigate if the transitions were observed. There were no neutron detectors used in that experiment but particle-

Figure 6.6: Spectra from particle-gated matrices extracted from the Galileo experiment. Panels (a), (b) and (c) show spectra gated on the 210-keV transition from αn -, αpn - and $\alpha 2pn$ -gated matrices, respectively.

gated cubes were created that were gated on protons and α particles. Since the transitions are observed in the α -, α p- and α 2p-gated matrices in the Galileo experiment cubes gated on α , α p and α 2p were analysed from the Gammasphere experiment. Figure 6.7 shows spectra

Figure 6.7: Triple coincidence spectra from particle-gated cubes from the Gammasphere experiment. The spectra in Panels (a) and (c) are double-gated on the 210- and 543-keV transitions in the α p- and α 2p-gated cubes, respectively. The spectra in Panels (b) and (d) are double-gated on the 210- and 603-keV transitions in the α p- and α 2p-gated cubes, respectively.

from α p- and α 2p-gated cubes which are double-gated on the 210- and 543-keV transitions and the 210- and 603-keV transitions. The γ rays with energies 210, 543, 603, 618, 638, 656 and 720 keV are present in both cubes however the transitions appear to be more intense in the α 2p-gated cube. This suggests that the transitions could be from this reaction channel. There is also the presence of a doublet at \sim 720 keV which is clear in the spectra from the α 2p-gated cube; this will be discussed later in this chapter.

It is reasonable to assume that the transitions are from an evaporation channel which involves the evaporation of at least one α particle, one proton and one neutron. If the evaporation channel of the nucleus involves at least one proton then it would not be possible for the transitions observed in this work to be from excited states in ^{116}Ba since this nucleus is from the α 2n evaporation channel.

Since the energy of the first 2^+ excited state in ^{116}Ba is expected to be between 220 and 250 keV, the α 2n-gated matrix from the Galileo data was used to search for transitions in this energy range. The projection from the α 2n-gated matrix was previously presented in Panel (a) of Figure 6.3. Within the 220-250 keV energy range, two peaks are observed in the projection of the α 2n-gated matrix and these have energies of 225 and 243 keV. When gating on these transitions the counts in the resulting spectra are too low for any conclusions to be drawn. Therefore, the α n-gated matrix was used to set these gates. The projection of the α n-gated matrix is shown in Panel (a) of Figure 6.8. The spectrum in Panel (b) is gated on 225 keV. In this spectrum the most intense peaks are from ^{116}Cs (α pn evaporation) in which there is a strong 225-keV transition. The unidentified transitions discussed above are also observed in this spectrum and these transitions are assigned to a nucleus in the following subsection. The spectrum in Panel (c) is gated on 243 keV and the dominant transitions in this spectrum are also from ^{116}Cs which also has a strong 243-keV transition. Several particle-gated matrices were analysed and the search for transitions in ^{116}Ba was unsuccessful.

Figure 6.8: Spectra from the αn -gated matrix from the Galileo experiment. The spectrum in Panel (a) is the projection, the spectrum in Panel (b) is gated on 225 keV and the spectrum in Panel (c) is gated on 243 keV.

6.2 Assigning the γ -ray transitions to a nucleus

As discussed in the previous section, there are several transitions that are observed in a number of particle-gated matrices from both experiments discussed in this work but which are not known in any nucleus that is populated. The methods used to determine the nucleus from which these transitions are emitted are discussed below. It can be said with some certainty that the transitions belong to a channel in which an α particle has been evaporated since

the transitions are more intense in spectra which are gated on an α particle. The transitions are also observed in spectra which are gated on one proton and two protons which implies that, in addition to an evaporated α particle, the evaporation channel will also have at least one proton. In order to determine whether the transitions belong to a channel with one or two evaporated protons the intensities of the unidentified transitions were measured in the 1p- and 2p-gated matrices. The ratio of these intensities were measured and compared to well-known transitions in neighbouring nuclei. Measuring the transitions in the 1p- and 2p-gated matrices, instead of an α p- and α 2p-gated matrix, gives the advantage that the unidentified transitions can be compared to a larger variety of nuclei from different evaporation channels. The neighbouring nuclei to which the unidentified transitions were compared

Figure 6.9: Plot showing the ratio of intensities of the unidentified transitions compared to well-known γ -ray transitions in neighbouring nuclei. The transitions were measured in the 1p- and 2p-gated matrices from the Gammasphere data. Panel (a) includes the ratio of intensities for different transitions in each nucleus and Panel (b) includes the weighted average for each nucleus. The nuclei and their respective evaporation channels are given.

are ^{116}Cs (αp evaporation), ^{119}Cs (3p), ^{115}I ($\alpha 3\text{p}$), ^{120}Ba (2p) and ^{116}Xe ($\alpha 2\text{p}$). The ratio of intensities for transitions in these nuclei in the 1p- and 2p-gated matrices are plotted in Figure 6.9. This was carried out using data from both experiments but for this plot data from the Gammasphere experiment were used. The ratio of intensities for the unidentified transitions are approximately equal to that of the transitions from ^{116}Xe which suggests that they are from a nucleus which involves the evaporation of an α particle and two protons. However, as already discussed, these transitions are observed in the Galileo experiment in matrices which are gated on one neutron. To investigate if the channel includes an evaporated neutron, the ratio of intensities were again studied. The unidentified transitions and transitions from neighbouring nuclei were measured in an αp - and αpn -gated matrix from

Figure 6.10: Plot showing the ratio of intensities of the unidentified transitions compared to well-known γ -ray transitions in neighbouring nuclei. The transitions were measured in the αp - and αpn -gated matrices from the Galileo data. Panel (a) includes the ratio of intensities for different transitions in each nucleus and Panel (b) includes the weighted average for each nucleus. The nuclei and their respective evaporation channels are given.

the Galileo experiment. This time, the matrices were gated on an α particle to eliminate transitions from the most intensely populated nuclei which have only protons in their reaction channels; such as ^{118}Xe (4p) and ^{119}Cs (3p). This allows transitions from reaction channels which involve the evaporation of one neutron to be observed more clearly. The nuclei in n-evaporation channels are produced with low cross sections and the spectra from n-gated matrices are dominated by transitions from 3p and 4p channels if the matrix is not also gated on at least one α particle. The neighbouring nuclei used for the ratio of intensities were ^{116}Xe (α 2p evaporation), ^{115}I (α 3p), ^{116}Cs (α pn) and ^{115}Xe (α 2pn). The ^{115}I and ^{116}Xe transitions are observed in the α pn-gated matrix because they are produced with large cross sections and also the detection efficiency of a neutron in the Neutron Wall is low. Transitions from ^{116}Xe (α 2p) and ^{115}I (α 3p) are present in the α pn-gated matrix if one and two protons miss detection, respectively, and if one neutron is misidentified. The non-detection and misidentification of particles is discussed in Section 5.5. The ratio of intensities of the transitions in the α p- and α pn-gated matrices are plotted in Figure 6.10. The unidentified transitions were observed clearly in these matrices and as a result five of them could be measured. This time the unidentified transitions do not lie in the same region as the α 2p transitions from ^{116}Xe but instead lie in the same region as the transitions from nuclei which involve the evaporation of a neutron. It may be concluded that the transitions observed in this work are from the α 2pn evaporation channel; this would mean that the transitions originate in ^{115}Xe .

Subsequently, the α 2p-gated matrix from the Gammasphere experiment was analysed. This matrix had fractions of matrices gated on the α 3p, α p and 2p evaporation channels subtracted which reduced the possibility of transitions from nuclei from these channels appearing in the spectra. In this matrix, gates were set on transitions emitted by nuclei from different channels to ensure that the background subtraction was successful. The results are shown in Figure 6.11. The spectra in Figure 6.11 are gated on the following transitions: (a) 210 keV (unidentified); (b) 394 keV (α 2p); (c) 415 keV (α 2pn); (d) 411 keV (α 3p); (e) 306 keV (α p) and (f) 191 keV (α pn). In each of these spectra, the most intense transitions are from ^{116}Xe . In the spectra which are gated on transitions in nuclei from channels which have

Figure 6.11: Spectra from the $\alpha 2p$ -gated matrix from the Gammasphere experiment. This matrix has fractions of the $\alpha 3p$ -, αp - and $2p$ -gated matrices subtracted. The nuclei and their respective evaporation channels are given and the transitions from these nuclei are denoted with different colours.

been subtracted negative peaks are seen at the positions where the coincident γ rays should be observed due to a slight oversubtraction of counts. This confirms that the subtraction has been successful. There are no neutron detectors used in the Gammasphere experiment therefore the subtracted matrix includes γ rays from evaporation channels which involve evaporated neutrons. For example ^{115}Xe transitions are still observed. The unidentified transitions are present in the subtracted matrix which further suggests that the transitions are from a channel which involves the evaporation of one α particle, two protons and possibly a neutron.

The mass of the nucleus from which specific γ rays are emitted can be determined using the FMA in the Gammasphere experiment. The PGAC spectrum produced at the focal plane of the FMA is discussed in Section 5.6 and is shown in Panel (a) of Figure 6.12. In this spectrum the intense A/q peaks which correspond to $A = 118$ and $A = 119$ are labelled. The small peak which corresponds to $A = 115$ is also labelled since it has been implied so far in this section that the unidentified transitions being investigated belong to ^{115}Xe . Four matrices were created which had γ -ray energy on the x axis and the PGAC spectrum on the y axis. Each of these matrices were gated on different evaporated particles; these were 2p, 3p, α 2p and α 3p. The γ -ray energy axis was gated at 210 keV and projected onto the PGAC axis in each matrix and the resulting spectra are shown in Panels (b), (c), (d) and (e) of Figure 6.12 for the 2p-, 3p-, α 2p- and α 3p-gated matrices, respectively. The peaks observed in each spectrum correspond mostly to the $A = 119$ peaks in the PGAC spectrum. However, in Panel (d), which is gated on α 2p, there is a slight broadening in one of the peaks observed. The broadening of this peak coincides with the $A = 115$ peak in the PGAC projection. The matrix was also sliced at 543 keV and the results were the same. There has been an intense rotational band reported in ^{119}Cs in which two of the low-lying intense transitions have energies of 210-keV and 550-keV [75]. The ^{119}Cs nucleus is produced with large cross sections in the experiment and since the energies of these low-lying transitions are similar to the unidentified transitions this explains why the $A = 119$ peaks are observed. The PGAC spectrum cannot be used to make a definitive assignment for the mass of the

Figure 6.12: Spectra from a matrix which has the PGAC spectrum on one axis and γ -ray energy on the other axis. Panel (a) shows the spectrum produced at the PGAC and the peaks corresponding to $A = 115$, $A = 118$ and $A = 119$ are labelled. The spectra in Panels (b), (c), (d) and (e) are gated at 210 keV on the γ -ray axis and are gated on 2p, 3p, α 2p and α 3p, respectively.

nucleus to which the transitions belong. This could potentially be why the transitions have not been assigned to ^{115}Xe in any previous work.

The FMA data suggest that the A value associated with the nucleus that emits the 210-keV

γ ray is 119. To ensure that the transitions do not belong to ^{119}Cs , data from a third experiment, which was performed at the University of Jyväskylä, were investigated. However, since the data from this experiment were not used extensively in this analysis, the experimental details and set up have not been discussed. The information about this experiment is discussed in detail in Ref. [76]. The $^{64}\text{Zn}(^{58}\text{Ni})$ reaction was used therefore the compound nucleus produced in this experiment was also ^{122}Ce . Transitions from ^{119}Cs are not observed in that data. This is presumably due to the higher beam energy of 290 MeV which was used. The new transitions identified in this work are observed in the data from that experiment which suggests that the transitions are not from ^{119}Cs .

The final method that was used to help identify the origin of the unidentified γ rays also involved the PGAC data from the focal plane of the FMA. Six $\gamma\gamma$ matrices were created which were gated on masses from $A = 115$ to $A = 120$. These six matrices were gated at 210 keV. The purpose of this was to identify the mass of the evaporation residue associated with the unidentified transitions. The results are shown in Figure 6.13; the spectra in Panels (a), (b), (c), (d), (e) and (f) are gated on $A = 115$, 116, 117, 118, 119 and 120, respectively. The transitions being investigated are observed in the matrices gated on $A = 115$, $A = 116$ and $A = 120$. The transitions are present in the $A = 116$ and $A = 120$ matrices because of charge-state ambiguities, as discussed in Section 5.6. The transitions are not observed in the $A = 119$ matrix, but the ^{119}Cs band which includes a 210-keV transition is observed. Since the transitions being investigated are not present in this spectrum it can be concluded that they do not belong to ^{119}Cs . In addition to the A/q gates, these matrices were also gated on $\alpha 2p$, since it has been suggested that the transitions are from the $\alpha 2p$ evaporation channel, however the statistics were too low for any conclusions to be drawn.

By comparing the ratio of intensities of different transitions in different channels, using the background subtracted particle-gated matrices and using the PGAC data it is proposed that the transitions observed in this work are emitted by ^{115}Xe produced in the $\alpha 2p$ evaporation channel.

Figure 6.13: Spectra from mass-gated matrices. The spectra in Panels (a), (b), (c), (d), (e) and (f) are gated on $A = 115, 116, 117, 118, 119$ and 120 , respectively. Each matrix is gated on the 210-keV transition. The intense peaks are labelled and the nucleus to which they belong are given.

6.3 Previous studies of neutron-deficient $A < 120$ xenon isotopes

The γ -ray transitions identified in this work have been assigned to ^{115}Xe ($Z = 54$, $N = 61$). Heavy-ion fusion-evaporation reactions and γ -ray spectroscopy have been used to populate and study excited states in neutron-deficient xenon isotopes with masses as low as $A = 110$. In the $A < 120$ xenon isotopes, excited states have been identified in $^{110-119}\text{Xe}$. Excited states were first identified in ^{119}Xe by Chowdhury *et al.* [77]. Since then the level scheme has been extended and currently eight bands have been identified [78–80]. The yrast band has been observed up to $55/2 \hbar$ (tentatively $83/2 \hbar$). Excited states were first identified in ^{118}Xe by Kerek *et al.* [81]. The level scheme has been extended significantly and, to date, eleven bands have been identified [82–84]. The ground-state band has been observed up to $14 \hbar$ (tentatively $38 \hbar$). Chowdhury *et al.* first identified excited states in ^{117}Xe [77]. Since then the level scheme has been extended to eight bands and the yrast band has been observed up to $55/2 \hbar$ (tentatively $91/2 \hbar$) [83,85]. Enhanced E1 transitions have been observed between two of the bands in ^{117}Xe . This is characteristic of octupole correlations and is discussed in detail in Ref. [17]. In ^{116}Xe , excited states were first identified by Janzen *et al.* [86,87]. Presently, the level scheme has been extended to eight bands and the ground-state band has been observed up to $16 \hbar$ (tentatively $44 \hbar$) [84]. Excited states were first identified in ^{115}Xe by Paul *et al.* [88]. Four bands have been identified and the yrast band has been observed to $39/2 \hbar$ [89]. The level scheme for ^{115}Xe is discussed in more detail in the following section. In ^{114}Xe , excited states were first identified by Rugari *et al.* [90]. More recently, ^{114}Xe was studied by Paul *et al.* and five bands were identified in that work [91]. The ground-state band has been observed up to $20 \hbar$ (tentatively $24 \hbar$) and a negative-parity side band has been observed which decays into the ground-state band via enhanced E1 transitions. The B(E1) strengths of these transitions are suggestive of octupole correlations and this is discussed in Ref. [15]. In ^{113}Xe , excited states were first identified by Paul *et al.* [92]. The most recent level scheme was developed by Scraggs *et al.* in which eight bands were identified [93]. The yrast

band was observed up to $31/2 \hbar$ (tentatively $43/2 \hbar$). Excited states were identified in ^{112}Xe by Smith *et al.* [14]. The level scheme for this nucleus consists of a ground-state band linked to a negative-parity side band. The ground-state band was observed up to $8 \hbar$ (tentatively $12 \hbar$) and the negative-parity band was observed up to $7 \hbar$ (tentatively $13 \hbar$). The two bands are linked together by three E1 transitions; one of which decays from a tentative 3^- state. This structure is characteristic of octupole deformation. The ground-state deformation of ^{112}Xe was inferred in the work by Smith *et al.* and was compared to the theoretical calculations performed by Möller, Nix, Myers and Swiatecki [32] and TRS calculations as discussed in Ref [14]. The ground-state deformation was larger than predicted by these calculations which could be explained by possible octupole correlations.

As discussed in Section 1.2, RDT can be used to study nuclei which decay by characteristic α and proton emission. The RDT method was used to study $^{110,111}\text{Xe}$. Five γ rays have been reported in the yrast band of ^{111}Xe [94]. However, only tentative spins and parities were assigned to the excited states in that work. In ^{110}Xe , three excited states have been reported in the ground-state band [95]. Again, only tentative spins and parities were assigned to these excited states. The deformation of the ground state in this nucleus also appeared to be larger than predicted by theoretical calculations.

6.4 Level scheme for ^{115}Xe

6.4.1 Previously published level scheme

Excited states were first identified in ^{115}Xe by Paul *et al.* in 1996, as reported in Ref. [88]. In that work, the reaction used was $^{60}\text{Ni}(^{58}\text{Ni}, 2pn)^{115}\text{Xe}$ in which the compound nucleus produced was ^{118}Ba . The 250-MeV ^{58}Ni beam was produced by the Tandem Accelerator Superconducting Cyclotron (TASCC) at Chalk River Laboratory in Canada and the target consisted of two self-supporting ^{60}Ni foils each with a thickness of $480 \mu\text{cm}^{-2}$. The level scheme published in that work includes only the yrast band which was proposed to be built

on orbitals from the $\nu h_{11/2}$ subshell. However, this is not necessarily the ground-state band. Systematics of neutron-deficient odd- A xenon isotopes show that the ground-state bands are usually based on orbitals from the $\nu d_{5/2}$ or $\nu g_{7/2}$ subshells. A smooth systematic behaviour of the excited states in this yrast band is observed when compared with neighbouring odd- A xenon isotopes. The most recent level scheme of ^{115}Xe was published by Paul *et al.* in 2000 and is discussed in Ref. [89]. In that work, the $^{60}\text{Ni}(^{58}\text{Ni},2pn)^{115}\text{Xe}$ reaction was used again and therefore the same compound nucleus of ^{118}Ba was produced. The 212 MeV ^{58}Ni beam was produced by the Vivitron Electrostatic Accelerator of the Institut de Recherches Subatomiques (IReS) at Strasbourg. The target in that experiment consisted of a self-

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Figure 6.14: Level scheme deduced by Paul *et al.* in 2000; this figure is extracted from Ref. [89]. The energies are given in keV and the width of the arrows are proportional to the γ -ray intensities. Each excited state is labelled with tentative spins and parities. The bands have been labelled A, B, C, and D for reference in this work.

supporting ^{60}Ni foil with a thickness of $230 \mu\text{gcm}^{-2}$. Four bands were identified in that work and the level scheme is shown in Figure 6.14. The yrast band, labelled as Band A, is observed up to spins of $39/2 \hbar$ and is linked to a positive-parity side band, Band B, by two γ -ray transitions. Band B is proposed to be based on the three quasiparticle $\nu h_{11/2} \otimes \pi h_{11/2} g_{7/2}$ configuration and is observed to spins of $41/2 \hbar$. This is consistent with analogous structures observed in $^{113,117,119}\text{Xe}$ [80,85,93]. Both Bands C and D are observed to decay to the ground state, which is proposed to be based on orbitals from the $\nu d_{5/2}$ subshell. These bands are proposed to be signature partners based on the $\nu g_{7/2}$ orbitals and they are observed up to spins of $25/2 \hbar$ and $23/2 \hbar$, respectively. Band B, can decay into Band C which can subsequently decay into Band D.

6.4.2 Level scheme for ^{115}Xe deduced in this work

In this work, new transitions have been assigned to ^{115}Xe and the current level scheme has been extended. The level scheme deduced in this work is shown in Figure 6.15. Bands 1, 2 and 3 are Bands A, B and C, respectively, in Figure 6.14. However, Band 4 is not analogous to Band D. The coincident γ rays which form Band D in Ref. [89] are not observed in this work. This will be discussed in more detail throughout this section.

The properties of the γ rays, such as their energies, intensities and angular distributions, were measured in order to determine the arrangement of the excited states from which they were emitted. The properties of the γ -ray transitions in each band are listed in Table A.1 in Appendix A. The analysis was mostly carried out using data from the Gammasphere experiment as this had several advantages such as higher particle-detection efficiencies which lead to less contamination in the spectra and the arrangement of the HPGe detectors in the array allowed angular distributions to be measured using the method discussed in Section 5.8. The level scheme will be discussed using spectra from the α 2p-gated cube. Relative spins and parities were assigned to the excited states using angular distribution measurements which was possible since there are γ -ray transitions which link the bands together. However, the

ground-state spin and parity was assigned using the systematics of neighbouring nuclei. Each band presented in Figure 6.15 will be discussed in the following sections.

6.4.2.1 Band 1

Band 1 is the yrast band in ^{115}Xe and has been previously identified [88, 89]. In this work, Band 1 is observed up to spins of $39/2 \hbar$ (tentatively $51/2 \hbar$). Spectra gated on γ -ray transitions in Band 1 are shown in Figure 6.16. Panel (a) shows a spectrum which is double-gated on the 415- and 635-keV transitions. Transitions in Band 1 are observed in this spectrum however some transitions from Band 2 are also seen. The energies of these transitions are 566, 578 and 723 keV. This suggests that Bands 1 and 2 are linked. Peaks are observed in the spectrum at 838 keV and 1038 keV which were previously identified by Paul *et al.* as linking

Figure 6.16: Triple coincidence spectra from the $\alpha 2p$ -gated cube from the Gammasphere experiment which show the Band 1 transitions in ^{115}Xe . The spectrum in Panel (a) is double-gated on the 415- and 635-keV transitions and the spectrum in Panel (b) is gated on any two transitions from the gatelist 415, 635, 768, 854, 920, 942 and 953 keV; that is, it is a sum of 21 double gates.

transitions between Bands 1 and 2. The spectrum presented in Panel (b) of Figure 6.16 is gated on several Band 1 transitions in the form of a gatelist; this means the spectrum is gated on any two of the transitions included in the gatelist. The gatelist used in Panel (b) includes the 415-, 635-, 768-, 854-, 920-, 942- and 953-keV transitions. The Band 2 transitions and the two linking transitions are significantly reduced in this spectrum. At ~ 1000 keV, a peak is observed in the γ -ray spectrum however it appears to be wider than the other peaks and is likely due to more than one γ ray. However, the exact transitions are indistinguishable in the spectra shown in Figure 6.16. In the first publication of the yrast band [88], there are transitions at 1005 keV, which decays from $43/2^- \rightarrow 39/2^-$, 1021 keV, which decays from $47/2^- \rightarrow 43/2^-$, and 1086 keV which decays from $51/2^- \rightarrow 47/2^-$. The peaks at ~ 1000 keV were investigated further and some of the spectra are shown in Figure 6.17. The spectra in Panels (a) and (b) are double-gated on 415 keV and any transition from the gatelist A; the energies of the γ rays in gatelist A are 920, 942 and 953 keV. In these spectra, the peaks at ~ 1000 keV are still indistinguishable but it is clear that there are γ rays present in the spectra. The spectra in Panels (c) and (d) are double-gated on 953 keV and any transition from the gatelist B; the energies of the γ rays in gatelist B are 415, 635 and 768 keV. In these spectra there are no peaks observed at ~ 1000 keV. The spectra in Panels (e) and (f) are double-gated on any transition from gatelist A and any transition from gatelist B. In these spectra, there are peaks observed at ~ 1000 keV but are not definitive enough to extract energies and intensities. In Figure 6.17, the peaks observed at ~ 1000 keV are labelled with the energies deduced by Paul *et al.* since the exact energies could not be measured. The transitions are added as tentative in the level scheme deduced in this work.

Figure 6.17: Triple coincidence spectra from the $\alpha 2p$ -gated cube from the Gammasphere experiment which are used to investigate the Band 1 transitions at ~ 1000 keV. The spectra in Panels (a) and (b) are double-gated on 415 keV and any transition from the gatelist with 920, 942 and 953 keV. The spectra in Panels (c) and (d) are double-gated on 953 keV and any transition from the gatelist with 415, 635 and 768 keV. The spectra in Panels (e) and (f) are double-gated on any transition from the gatelist with 415, 635 and 768 keV and any transition from the gatelist with 920, 942 and 953 keV.

6.4.2.2 Band 2

Band 2 is observed up to spins of $41/2 \hbar$. Some of the Band 2 transitions are observed in Panel (a) of Figure 6.16. The spectra in Figure 6.18 are included to show the positions of the

linking transitions between Bands 1 and 2. The spectrum in Panel (a) is double-gated on the 415- and 768-keV transitions from Band 1. When gating on 768 keV the 1038-keV transitions which decays from Band 2 to Band 1 is no longer observed. The 566-keV transition from Band 2 is also not observed which is consistent with the position of the linking transition in the level scheme of Figure 6.15. However, the 838-keV transition, which decays from Band 2 to Band 1, and Band 2 transitions with energies of 578, 723 and 892 keV are still observed. The 1021-keV transitions which decays from $41/2^+ \rightarrow 37/2^+$ is not observed in spectra which are gated on Band 1 transitions. If it is present it will be in the region of the transitions at ~ 1000 keV in which the peaks in the spectrum cannot be distinguished. Spectra were analysed with gates set on the Band 2 transitions however the spectra were always highly contaminated with intense transitions from neighbouring nuclei. The 1021-keV transition is observed in a spectrum gated on Band 4 transitions as discussed below. The spectrum in Panel (b) is double-gated on the 415- and 854-keV transitions from Band 1. In this spectrum,

Figure 6.18: Triple coincidence spectra from the $\alpha 2p$ -gated cube from the Gammasphere experiment. The spectrum in Panel (a) is double-gated on the 415- and 768-keV transitions in Band 1. The spectrum in Panel (b) is double-gated on the 415- and 854-keV transitions in Band 1.

the Band 2 transitions and the links between Bands 1 and 2 are not observed. Since no Band 2 transitions are observed in this spectrum, it is unlikely that there are transitions above the $23/2^-$ state which decay from Band 2 to Band 1. The spectra discussed here confirm that the positions of the 838- and 1038-keV linking transition between Bands 1 and 2 are correct. The angular distributions of these transitions could not be measured but based on systematics of neighbouring nuclei they are proposed to be E1 transitions.

6.4.2.3 Band 3

Band 3 is observed up to spins of $17/2 \hbar$ (tentatively $25/2 \hbar$). The spectrum in Panel (a) of Figure 6.19 is double-gated on the 350- and 558-keV transitions from Band 3. The 221-keV transition is observed which decays from $5/2^+$ to the proposed ground state. There is also a peak observed at approximately 600 keV; this peak is expected to include the 600-keV transition in Band 3 and the 604-keV transition which decays from Band 2 to Band 3. However, none of the Band 2 transitions are observed in this spectrum. This is possibly because the 604-keV transition which decays from Band 2 to Band 3 appears to be quite weak and also the Band 2 transitions in general are weak relative to other transitions in this nucleus. The spectrum in Panel (b) is gated on any two transitions from the gatelist which includes the 350-, 558- and 600-keV transitions from Band 3. In this spectrum, the 566- and 578-keV transitions are observed thus confirming that there is a link between Bands 2 and 3. The peak at approximately 600 keV in this spectrum includes contributions from the 600-keV transition in Band 3 and the 604-keV transition which decays from Band 2 to Band 3. Paul *et al.* have included an additional two transitions in Band 3 (labelled Band C in Figure 6.14) at energies of 672 and 632 keV. These transitions were not clearly observed in any experimental data used in the present work however they have been included in the level scheme as tentative transitions. These are included as tentative transitions since any gates set on the Band 3 transitions result in spectra in which weak transitions at these energies could be buried in the background.

Figure 6.19: Triple coincidence spectra from the $\alpha 2p$ -gated cube from the Gammasphere experiment. The spectrum in Panel (a) is double-gated on the 350- and 558-keV transitions from Band 3. The spectrum in Panel (b) is gated on any two transitions from the gatelist with energies 350, 558 and 600 keV.

6.4.2.4 Band 4

The discussion and spectra presented in the previous subsections have shown that the excited states in Bands A, B and C published by Paul *et al.* in Ref. [89] are observed in this work. However, the γ -ray transitions in Band D by Paul *et al.* are not observed in the Gammasphere or Galileo experiment; these transitions have energies of 208, 501, 575, 660 and 737 keV. The data from the University of Jyväskylä were also analysed to investigate if these transitions were observed. The spectrum shown in Figure 6.20 is double-gated on 208 and 501-keV. The γ -ray transitions observed in this spectrum belong to ^{114}I [96]. Transitions with the same energies as those proposed in Band D are coincident transitions in ^{114}I therefore when gating on any of these transitions the transitions from ^{114}I dominate in the spectra. Since the transitions in Band D are not observed in the Galileo experiment or Gammasphere experiment

Figure 6.20: Triple coincidence spectrum from a cube from the experiment performed at the University of Jyväskylä. This spectrum is double-gated on 208 and 501 keV. The transitions labelled in this spectrum belong to ^{114}I .

they are not included in the level scheme deduced in the present work. It is possible that the transitions assigned to Band D by Paul *et al.* are misassigned transitions from ^{114}I , but this assertion would need further investigation.

The transitions observed in this work form a new band in ^{115}Xe which will be referred to as Band 4 in this discussion. The arrangement of excited states, from which these γ -ray transitions are emitted, and the search for transitions which could link Band 4 to the previously identified bands in ^{115}Xe is discussed below. The new transitions have energies of 210, 543, 603, 618, 636, 658 and 720 keV. The spectra shown in Figure 6.21 are gated on some of these transitions. Panel (a) shows a spectrum double-gated on 210 and 543 keV. Additional, less intense, transitions are observed at 374, 415 and 550 keV. The latter two are contamination from transitions in ^{119}Cs since the gated energies are similar to intense transitions in that nucleus. The transition at 374 keV could possibly be a transition which links Band 4 to another band in ^{115}Xe . However, no transitions from other bands are seen in this spectrum. The linking transitions will be discussed later in this section. The spectra in Panels (b) and (c) are double-gated on 543 and 638 keV and 603 and 659 keV, respectively. In these spectra, the only transitions observed are from Band 4. In the spectrum in Panel (b), a peak is observed at 835 keV which is proposed to be another transition in this band.

Figure 6.21: Triple coincidence spectra from the $\alpha 2p$ -gated cube from the Gammasphere experiment which show the Band 4 transitions. The spectrum in Panel (a) is double-gated on the 210- and 543-keV transitions, the spectrum in Panel (b) is double-gated on 543- and 638-keV transitions and the spectrum in Panel (c) is double-gated on the 603- and 659-keV transitions.

The spectra in Figure 6.22 show the high-spin transitions in Band 4. The spectrum in Panel (a) is double-gated on 210 keV and any transition from the gatelist which includes the 638- and 659-keV transitions. The spectrum in Panel (b) is gated on any two transitions from the gatelist with energies of 210, 543, 603, 638, 659 and 720 keV. The transition at 618 keV is not included in this gatelist as it increases contamination from ^{116}Xe transitions since the energy is similar to that of the 616-keV transition in the yrast band of that nucleus. There are peaks observed at 835 and 939 keV in these spectra which appear to be additional transitions in

Figure 6.22: Triple coincidence spectrum from the $\alpha 2p$ -gated cube from the Gammasphere experiment. The spectrum in Panel (a) is double-gated on 210 keV and any transition from the gatelist which includes the 638- and 659-keV transitions. The spectrum in Panel (b) is gated on any two transitions from the gatelist with 210, 543, 603, 638, 659 and 720 keV.

Band 4. The spectra also include small peaks at 892 and 1021 keV. There are transitions with these energies in Band 2 which suggests that transitions exist which link Band 4 to Band 2.

The 720-keV peak appears wider in most of the spectra and further investigation has shown that it is actually the result of two different transitions with energies of 720 and 724 keV. Spectra which show the peaks at these energies are shown in Figure 6.23. The spectrum in Panel (a) is double-gated on 210 and 543 keV, the spectrum in Panel (b) is double-gated on 210 and 603 keV and the spectrum in Panel (c) is double-gated on 543 and 603 keV. It is clear from these spectra that two peaks are present. Energy and intensity measurements of the γ rays have been used to determine the arrangement of excited states in Band 4 as shown in Figure 6.15.

Figure 6.23: Spectra from the $\alpha 2p$ -gated cube from the Gammasphere experiment which show the Band 4 transitions at 720 and 724 keV. The spectrum in Panel (a) is double-gated on 210 and 543 keV, the spectrum in Panel (b) is double-gated on 210 and 603 keV and the spectrum in Panel (c) is double-gated on 543 and 603 keV.

There are some transitions observed in the spectra presented in this section that have not been fully discussed. In Panel (a) of Figure 6.21, the spectrum is gated on 210 keV however a peak is still observed at 209 keV. Figure 6.24 shows five spectra. Each of which is gated on the 210-keV transition and another transition; the latter transitions are 543, 603, 618, 638 and 658 keV for Panels (a), (b), (c), (d) and (e), respectively. In each of these spectra, a peak is observed at 209 keV. This transition could possibly be a linking transition between Band 4 and another band in ^{115}Xe . The spectrum shown in Figure 6.25 is double-gated on the 209- and 210-keV transitions. In this spectrum, the transitions in Band 4 are observed up to 720 keV. Therefore, it is unlikely that the 209-keV transition is a low-lying linking transition in the band and implies that it feeds into Band 4 at the $31/2^+$ state. In Figure 6.22, the 892- and 1021-keV transitions from Band 2 are observed which suggests that there may be a linking transition between Band 2 and Band 4. The spectra discussed here suggest that

Figure 6.24: Triple coincidence spectra from the $\alpha 2p$ -gated cube from the Gammasphere experiment. Each spectrum is gated on 210 keV and another transition; these transitions are 543, 603, 618, 638 and 659 keV for Panels (a), (b), (c), (d) and (e), respectively.

there is a linking transition which decays from $33/2^+$ state in Band 2 to $31/2^+$ state in Band 4 with an energy of 209 keV.

In Panel (b) of Figure 6.24, peaks are observed at 361 and 374 keV. These are also proposed to be transitions which link Band 4 to other bands in ^{115}Xe . There is a 361-keV transition

Figure 6.25: Triple coincidence spectrum from an α 2p-gated cube from the Gammasphere experiment. This spectrum is double-gated on the 209- and 210-keV transitions.

in the previously published level scheme which decays from the $9/2^+$ state in Band 3. In Figure 6.24, the 361-keV transition is only observed in Panel (b). The 558-keV transition in Band 3 and the 566- and 578-keV from Band 2 are also observed in this spectrum. Although this gate was set on the 603-keV transition from Band 4 if there are low-lying transitions which decay from Band 3 to Band 4 then there would be contamination in this spectrum from the transition at 600 keV in Band 3. This would explain why the transitions in Bands 2 and 3 are observed. The 361-keV transition is not observed in the spectrum which is gated on 350 and 558 keV, shown in Panel (a) of Figure 6.19. The transition is also not observed in the spectrum gated on 210 and 543 keV. This suggests that the 361-keV transition decays from the $9/2^+$ state of Band 3 to the $7/2^+$ state of Band 4.

The transition at 374 keV is observed in Panels (a) and (b) of Figure 6.24. This transition is not observed in any spectrum which is gated above the $15/2^+$ state in Band 4. Since there are low-lying transitions with similar energies at approximately 600 keV in Bands 3 and 4, there was difficulty in determining the position of this linking transition. The transition could decay from the $13/2^+$ state of Band 3 to the $11/2^+$ state of Band 4, from the $17/2^+$ state of Band 3 to the $15/2^+$ state of Band 4 or there could be a transition decaying from both of these states. The transition is positioned on the level scheme as the decay from the $13/2^+$ state in Band 3 to the $11/2^+$ state in Band 4. However, a tentative transition has also

Figure 6.26: Triple coincidence spectrum from and $\alpha 2p$ -gated cube from the Gammasphere experiment. The spectrum in Panel (a) is double-gated on 210 and 558 keV and the spectrum in Panel (b) is double-gated on 543 and 600 keV.

been added which decays from the $17/2^+$ state in Band 3 to the $15/2^+$ state in Band 4.

The spectra shown in Figure 6.26 are included to further support the positioning of the linking transitions discussed above. The spectrum in Panel (a) is double-gated on the 210-keV transition from Band 4 and the 558-keV transition from Band 3. In this spectrum there is a peak observed at 361 keV which is the transition that decays from the $9/2^+$ state in Band 3 to the $7/2^+$ state in Band 4. There is also a peak observed at 600 keV which is the transition in Band 3 however this peak will also likely have contributions from the 604-keV transition which decays from the $21/2^+$ state in Band 2 to the $17/2^+$ state in Band 3. When gating on the 210-keV transition, a peak is usually observed at 209 keV however this is not the case here. This supports the decision that the 209-keV transition is positioned above the $7/2^+$ state in Band 4. The spectrum in Panel (b) of Figure 6.26 is double-gated on the 543-keV transition in Band 4 and the 600-keV transition in Band 3. The Band 4 transitions are observed in this spectrum as it is contaminated from the 603-keV transition in Band 4.

There is a small peak observed at 374 keV which is the transition that decays from Band 3 to Band 4.

Chapter 7

Discussion

7.1 Total Routhian Surface (TRS) calculations

The total Routhian of a nucleus describes the energy in the rotating frame, and is often plotted as a function of the deformation parameters such as β_2 , β_4 and γ . Total Routhian Surface (TRS) calculations, described in Ref. [97–100], can be used to determine the deformation parameters for the likely quasiparticle configurations of the odd neutron in ^{115}Xe . The total Routhian of the nucleus is minimised with respect to the β_2 , β_4 and γ for a given number of quasiparticles with signature α and parity π . The calculations are often carried out at steps in rotational frequency ω resulting in deformation parameters for each frequency. The signature and parity are the only conserved quantum numbers in the TRS calculations and the orbitals associated with the configurations of the odd neutron are characterised by these parameters. The likely configurations can be determined by identifying the orbitals which lie near to the Fermi surface and by investigating the systematic behaviour of other odd- A xenon isotopes. The Nilsson orbitals near to the Fermi Surface for both neutrons and protons are listed in Table 7.1 and are labelled using standard nomenclature, as given in Ref. [43, 101].

In this work, TRS calculations were carried out for different configurations of the odd neutron

Table 7.1: Adopted nomenclature for orbitals near the Fermi surface in ^{115}Xe .

	Subshell	$\Omega^\pi [Nn_z\Lambda]$	$\alpha = -\frac{1}{2}$	$\alpha = \frac{1}{2}$
Neutrons	$d_{5/2}g_{7/2}$	$\frac{5}{2}^+ [413]$	B	A
	$d_{5/2}g_{7/2}$	$\frac{3}{2}^+ [411]$	D	C
	$h_{11/2}$	$\frac{3}{2}^- [541]$	E	F
	$h_{11/2}$	$\frac{1}{2}^- [550]$	G	H
Protons	$d_{5/2}g_{7/2}$	$\frac{3}{2}^+ [422]$	b	a
	$d_{5/2}g_{7/2}$	$\frac{1}{2}^+ [420]$	d	c
	$h_{11/2}$	$\frac{1}{2}^- [550]$	e	f
	$h_{11/2}$	$\frac{3}{2}^- [541]$	g	h

and the plots for the four lowest ω values for each configuration are shown in Appendix B. The β_2 , β_4 and γ values were extracted at $\omega = 0.191 \text{ MeV}\hbar^{-1}$ as this rotational frequency is expected to be below the first quasiparticle alignment. The deformation parameters for each configuration at this frequency are listed in Table 7.2. It can be seen that the β_2 and β_4 deformation parameters do not vary significantly. The γ parameters are mostly within 3° of zero however for the A and H configurations $\gamma = -120^\circ$.

Table 7.2: The β_2 , β_4 and γ deformations obtained from the TRS calculations for ^{115}Xe at rotational frequency of $0.191 \text{ MeV}\hbar^{-1}$.

$\nu (\pi, \alpha)$	β_2	β_4	γ
A(+,+)	0.200	0.027	-120.0
B(+,-)	0.223	0.040	-2.0
C(+,+)	0.212	0.034	2.1
D(+,-)	0.213	0.035	0.4
E(-,-)	0.212	0.030	-2.3
F(-,+)	0.222	0.036	1.8
G(-,-)	0.219	0.032	0.3
H(-,+)	0.196	0.025	-120.0

7.2 Cranked Shell Model (CSM) calculations

Cranked shell model (CSM) calculations can be used to investigate the theoretical behaviour of quasiparticles with a given configuration. In this work, the deformation parameters extracted from the TRS calculations were used in CSM calculations with a Wood-Saxon potential [102,103]. Quasiparticle diagrams are produced from the CSM calculations which can be used to predict the behaviour of the quasiparticles in different orbitals with respect to the rotational frequency. Theoretical information such as alignment frequencies and interaction strengths can be extracted from the quasiparticle diagrams and can be compared to experimental results. Consequently CSM calculations can assist in assigning configurations to rotational bands in a given nucleus. This is discussed in Section 7.3.

Examples of quasiparticle diagrams for protons and neutrons are shown in Figure 7.1. The lines in the diagram represent the orbitals with different combinations of signature and parity which can be occupied by the quasiparticles. When the rotational frequency ω is zero the

quasiparticle orbitals are equivalent to the Nilsson model orbitals for the specified deformation. However, as the rotational frequency is increased the orbitals with different values of signature separate and as a result the signature and parity become the only good quantum numbers. Only one quasiparticle can occupy each orbital. The solid and dotted lines rep-

Figure 7.1: Quasiparticle diagrams for protons ($Z = 54$) and neutrons ($N = 61$) produced by cranked shell model calculations. The deformation parameters used were $\beta_2 = 0.212$, $\beta_4 = 0.032$ and $\gamma = 0^\circ$. The solid and dotted lines represent the positive-parity orbitals while the dashed and dot-dashed lines represent the negative-parity orbitals. The negative-parity orbitals have been labelled using standard nomenclature and the crossings of these orbitals have been indicated.

represent the positive-parity orbitals with positive and negative signature, respectively. The orbitals from the intruder negative-parity subshell are of interest here since the alignments in the nuclei in the $A < 120$ region are predominantly due to the alignment of $h_{11/2}$ protons or neutrons. In the quasiparticle diagrams, the negative-parity orbitals are represented by the dashed and dot-dashed lines which have negative and positive signature, respectively. For the example shown in Figure 7.1, the negative-parity trajectories are labelled with the standard nomenclature used in Table 7.1. The quasiparticle trajectories are reflected around the line at 0 MeV on the Routhian axis and the reflected trajectories are called the *conjugate levels*. These conjugate levels have the same parity as their partners but have opposite signature; for example the trajectory labelled E in Panel (a) of Figure 7.1 has negative signature (represented by the dashed line) and the conjugate partner labelled -E has positive signature (represented by dot-dashed line). When a level is occupied the conjugate level is always unoccupied. The quasiparticle trajectories which have the same parity and signature do not mix but repel one another. The repulsion is described as a *crossing* between trajectories and character is exchanged when this occurs. This is illustrated, for example, in Panel (a) of Figure 7.1 when the trajectory labelled F and the conjugate level labelled -E approach one another. It can be seen that the trajectories are repelled and the -E orbital becomes F and vice versa. The rotational frequency at which the crossings are observed correspond to the theoretical alignment frequency; the alignment frequencies are labelled in Figure 7.1 for the different crossings of both protons and neutrons. For example, the crossing labelled νEF corresponds to the lowest-lying alignment of a pair of $h_{11/2}$ neutrons. The distance between the trajectories when the crossing occurs is related to the interaction strength. If the spacing is small then the interaction is expected to be stronger. This would mean that the backbend observed experimentally as a result of this alignment is expected to be sharper.

The deformation parameters extracted from the TRS calculations, presented in Table 7.2, show that there are small variations in the β_2 , β_4 and γ parameters for the likely configurations of the odd neutron. This is with the exception of the A and H configuration in which the γ value varies significantly. In order to investigate the effect that the individual deformation

parameters have on the predicted alignment frequencies, CSM calculations were carried out where two of the three deformation parameters were fixed and the third was systematically varied. The ranges for which these were carried out were $0.05 \leq \beta_2 \leq 0.35$, $0 \leq \beta_4 \leq 0.06$ and $-10^\circ \leq \gamma \leq 20^\circ$. For each of the deformation parameters, the alignment frequencies were extracted from the quasiparticle diagrams for both neutrons and protons and plotted against the varying deformation parameters, the results are shown in Figure 7.2. There is very little change in the alignment frequencies for the β_4 and γ deformation parameters over the selected range of values. However, the alignment frequency varies more with the β_2

Figure 7.2: Investigation of the ν EF and π EF alignment frequencies obtained from the cranked shell model calculations. Panels (a), (b) and (c) show the alignment frequencies of pairs of $h_{11/2}$ neutrons for varying β_2 , β_4 and γ , respectively. Panels (d), (e) and (f) show the alignment frequencies of pairs of $h_{11/2}$ protons for varying β_2 , β_4 and γ , respectively. The parameters which are not being measured are fixed to $\beta_2 = 0.212$, $\beta_4 = 0.032$ and $\gamma = 0^\circ$.

Table 7.3: Alignment frequencies extracted from CSM calculations using $\beta_2 = 0.212$, $\beta_4 = 0.032$ and $\gamma = 0^\circ$.

orbital	ω (MeV \hbar^{-1})	orbital	ω (MeV \hbar^{-1})
ν EF	0.31	π ef	0.44
ν FG	0.45	π fg	0.69
ν EH	0.47	π eh	0.65

deformation parameter. The β_2 values extracted from the TRS calculations for the likely configurations are all approximately 0.2 therefore the alignment frequencies are expected to be relatively consistent. Average values of the β_2 , β_4 and γ deformation parameters from the TRS calculations were used to produce the quasiparticle diagrams for ^{115}Xe which are shown in Figure 7.1; the parameters used were $\beta_2 = 0.212$, $\beta_4 = 0.032$ and $\gamma = 0^\circ$. Theoretical alignment frequencies for both neutrons and proton crossings were extracted from the quasiparticle diagrams and are given in Table 7.3. The distance between the quasiparticle trajectories at these crossings suggest that the ν EF alignment has a smaller interaction strength than the π ef alignment therefore experimentally the ν EF alignment is expected to have a more pronounced backbend. However, the interaction strengths of the ν FG and ν EH alignments are larger than that of the π fg and π eh alignments and the latter will be expected to have a more pronounced backbend.

7.3 Aligned angular momenta

The aligned angular momenta i_x of excited states can be used to help infer the underlying configuration of a given band. In this work, the experimental aligned angular momenta in ^{115}Xe were extracted from the data and plotted using the equations discussed in Section 2.9. A reference was subtracted which was defined by Harris parameters [47]; the parameters used were $\mathcal{J}_0 = 15 \hbar^2 \text{MeV}^{-1}$ and $\mathcal{J}_1 = 25 \hbar^4 \text{MeV}^{-3}$. These values were chosen as they have been

used previously in the study of ^{115}Xe and some neighbouring nuclei [84,88,91]. Using the same Harris parameters allows a more precise comparison of aligned angular momenta in different nuclei. The aligned angular momenta in ^{115}Xe are presented and discussed in the following section in which blocking arguments are used to suggest possible underlying configurations for each band. The experimental alignment frequencies are compared to the theoretical ones extracted from the CSM calculations. The alignments in ^{115}Xe are also compared to those of yrast bands in some neighbouring nuclei.

7.3.1 Aligned angular momenta in neighbouring nuclei

The aligned angular momenta of the yrast bands in some neighbouring nuclei of ^{115}Xe have been analysed in order to investigate the behaviour of the πef and νEF alignments. The aligned angular momenta of the yrast bands in ^{116}Xe , ^{117}Xe and ^{117}Cs are plotted with respect to rotational frequency in Figure 7.3. The differences in the backbends which result from the πef and νEF alignments are observed. In the yrast band of ^{116}Xe , there is an even number of protons and neutrons. Therefore, the protons and neutrons are paired and so the πef and νEF alignments are both observed since the neither alignment is blocked. Two gradual backbends are observed which are due to the πef and νEF alignments, at $\sim 0.39 \text{ MeV}\hbar^{-1}$ and $\sim 0.51 \text{ MeV}\hbar^{-1}$ in Figure 7.3, respectively. Although the rotational frequencies of the alignments observed in ^{116}Xe are different from those predicted in ^{115}Xe , the shape of the backbends resulting from the alignments can be compared for protons and neutrons. The ^{116}Xe alignments and band configurations are discussed by Sears *et al.* in Ref. [84]. In the yrast band of ^{117}Xe , the odd neutron occupies the lowest $\nu h_{11/2}$ orbital therefore the νEF alignment is blocked. As a result, only the πef alignment is observed and this is seen at $\sim 0.42 \text{ MeV}\hbar^{-1}$. The ^{117}Xe alignments and band configurations are discussed by Paul *et al.* in Ref. [85]. In the yrast band of ^{117}Cs , the odd proton occupies the lowest $\pi h_{11/2}$ orbital therefore blocking the πef alignment. The νEF alignment is observed at $\sim 0.35 \text{ MeV}\hbar^{-1}$. The alignments and band configurations of ^{117}Cs are discussed by Smith *et al.* in Ref. [104]. The backbend resulting from the πef alignment in ^{117}Xe is more pronounced than the backbend

Figure 7.3: Aligned angular momenta plotted against rotational frequency for the yrast bands in some neighbouring nuclei of ^{115}Xe . The alignments are shown for ^{117}Cs [104], ^{116}Xe [84] and ^{117}Xe [85]. A reference with Harris parameters of $\mathcal{J}_0 = 15 \hbar^2\text{MeV}^{-1}$ and $\mathcal{J}_1 = 25 \hbar^4\text{MeV}^{-3}$ has been subtracted.

resulting from the νEF alignment in ^{117}Cs which is gradual. The vertical distance between the trajectories in the quasiparticle diagrams, shown in Figure 7.1, suggest that this will not be the case in ^{115}Xe but the νEF alignment will be less gradual than the πef alignment. The alignments in the yrast bands of ^{116}Xe , ^{117}Xe and ^{117}Cs will be used in the discussion of the ^{115}Xe alignments in the following section, for comparison.

The level scheme for ^{115}Xe exhibits a similar structure to that of four bands previously identified in ^{113}Xe . The entire level scheme for ^{113}Xe is discussed by Scraggs *et al.* in Ref. [93] and the bands which have a similar structure to ^{115}Xe are shown in Figure 7.4. The numbering of the bands has been adopted from Ref. [93]. In that work, Band 3 is predicted to be based on the E configuration with the odd neutron occupying the $\nu h_{11/2}[541]3/2^-$ Nilsson orbital.

The likely configuration of Band 4 is predicted to be Eeb which is a three-quasiparticle configuration based on $\nu h_{11/2}[541]3/2^- \otimes \pi h_{11/2}[550]1/2^- \pi g_{7/2}[422]3/2^+$. Bands 6 and 7 are predicted to have the configuration of A and B, respectively. This corresponds to the positive and negative signature of the $\nu g_{7/2}[413]5/2^+$ Nilsson orbital. In the work by Paul *et al.*, the four bands identified in ^{115}Xe are proposed to have the configurations of E, Eeb, A and B (see Figure 6.14) [89]. These configurations are the same as the analogous bands in ^{113}Xe however no alignments are discussed in the work by Paul *et al.*. The alignments of the ^{115}Xe bands observed in the present work are discussed below.

Figure 7.4: Partial level scheme deduced by Scraggs *et al.* in Ref. [93]. The energies of the transitions are given in keV and the widths of the arrows are proportional to the relative γ -ray intensities.

7.3.2 Aligned angular momenta in ^{115}Xe

The aligned angular momenta for each band in ^{115}Xe are plotted with respect to rotational frequency in Figure 7.5. The theoretical νEF and πef alignment frequencies, which were extracted from CSM calculations, are indicated on the plot with dashed lines. In Figure 7.6, the aligned angular momenta of each band in ^{115}Xe are compared to the alignments in the yrast bands of ^{116}Xe , ^{117}Xe and ^{117}Cs . The alignments in each band of ^{115}Xe are discussed below and possible configurations are suggested.

Band 1 has been previously identified as the yrast band in ^{115}Xe . In the neighbouring odd- A xenon isotopes, the yrast bands have been assigned to be based on the E configuration.

Figure 7.5: Aligned angular momentum plotted against rotational frequency for each of the bands in ^{115}Xe . A reference with Harris parameters of $\mathcal{J}_0 = 15 \hbar^2\text{MeV}^{-1}$ and $\mathcal{J}_1 = 25 \hbar^4\text{MeV}^{-3}$ has been subtracted [89]. The νEF and πef alignment frequencies, predicted from cranked shell model calculations, are indicated on the plot.

In Band 1, there is no backbend observed at $\sim 0.31 \text{ MeV}\hbar^{-1}$ which is the predicted νEF alignment frequency. At this frequency the aligned angular momentum remains relatively constant which implies that the alignment is blocked by a quasineutron. However, there is a backbend observed at $\sim 0.43 \text{ MeV}\hbar^{-1}$ which occurs over $\sim 0.04 \text{ MeV}\hbar^{-1}$. The gain in aligned angular momentum at this backbend is $\sim 5.5 \hbar$. This could be the result of the πef alignment predicted to occur at $\sim 0.44 \text{ MeV}\hbar^{-1}$. The νFG and νEH alignments are also predicted to occur at $\sim 0.45 \text{ MeV}\hbar^{-1}$ and $\sim 0.47 \text{ MeV}\hbar^{-1}$, respectively. If the band is based on the E configuration then the νEH alignment would be blocked along with the νEF alignment. The gradual nature of the backbend at $\sim 0.43 \text{ MeV}\hbar^{-1}$ further suggests that it is due to the πef alignment. This is based on the interaction strengths from the quasiparticle diagrams which suggest that the πef alignment is expected to be more gradual than the νEF alignment. However, an additional backbend is observed at $\sim 0.46 \text{ MeV}\hbar^{-1}$ which appears to be more abrupt. This is likely to be due to the νFG alignment which is predicted to occur at $\sim 0.45 \text{ MeV}\hbar^{-1}$. The observation of the νFG alignment further suggests that Band 1 is based on the E configuration. The aligned angular momentum in Band 1 has been compared to that of the yrast bands in ^{116}Xe , ^{117}Xe and ^{117}Cs ; this plot is shown in Panel (a) of Figure 7.6. The backbend observed at $\sim 0.43 \text{ MeV}\hbar^{-1}$ in Band 1 follows a similar trend to the backbend observed in the yrast band of ^{117}Xe which further supports the assignment of an E configuration to Band 1 in ^{115}Xe . Following the analysis of the alignments, Band 1 is interpreted to be based on the intruder-parity $\nu h_{11/2}[541]3/2^-$ orbital.

In Band 2, there are no backbends observed at the predicted νEF and πef alignment frequencies. The aligned angular momentum remains relatively constant in this band. This suggests that both the νEF and πef alignments could be blocked. The blocking of both alignments could imply that this band could be the result of the breaking of another pair of quasiparticles following the Band 1 alignment. This would mean that Band 2 could be a three-quasiparticle configuration. If this is the case then the three-quasiparticle configuration may involve $\nu h_{11/2}$ and $\pi h_{11/2}$ quasiparticles since both the νEF and πef alignments appear to be blocked. Band 2 has been previously reported to be based on the Eeb configuration

by Paul *et al.*. The aligned angular momentum in Band 2 is compared to the yrast bands of neighbouring nuclei in Panel (b) of Figure 7.6. However, the alignment in this band does not follow a similar trend to the yrast band alignment data. Based on the alignment data, previous assignments, and systematics of neighbouring nuclei, Band 2 is interpreted to be based on the $\nu h_{11/2}[541]3/2^- \otimes \pi h_{11/2}[550]1/2^- \pi g_{7/2}[422]3/2^+$ three-quasiparticle configuration.

In Band 3, a sharp backbend is seen between $\sim 0.26 \text{ MeV}\hbar^{-1}$ and $\sim 0.30 \text{ MeV}\hbar^{-1}$. This

Figure 7.6: Aligned angular momenta plotted against rotational frequency for each of the bands in ^{115}Xe . Each plot also includes the aligned angular momenta in the yrast bands of ^{116}Xe , ^{117}Xe and ^{117}Cs . A reference with Harris parameters of $\mathcal{J}_0 = 15 \text{ } \hbar^2\text{MeV}^{-1}$ and $\mathcal{J}_1 = 25 \text{ } \hbar^4\text{MeV}^{-3}$ has been subtracted [89].

could be the result of the ν EF alignment which is predicted to occur at $\sim 0.31 \text{ MeV}\hbar^{-1}$. Only five excited states have been observed in this band, two of which are tentative, and the aligned angular momentum is not observed above $\sim 0.32 \text{ MeV}\hbar^{-1}$. The gain in aligned angular momentum cannot be determined as the end of the alignment is not seen due to the lack of excited states observed in Band 3. The proton alignments are predicted to occur above this rotational frequency therefore it cannot be determined whether or not they occur. Paul *et al.* have previously assigned Band 3 to be based on the A configuration. If the backbend at $\sim 0.31 \text{ MeV}\hbar^{-1}$ is the result of ν EF alignment, this implies the $\nu h_{11/2}$ orbital is unoccupied before the alignment and the A configuration is a reasonable assignment. When compared to the alignments in the yrast bands of the neighbouring nuclei, shown in Panel (c) of Figure 7.6, the alignment in Band 3 follows a similar trend to the first alignment in the yrast band of ^{116}Xe . However, the alignment in ^{116}Xe is due to the π ef alignment which occurs before, and is more abrupt than the ν EF alignment but in ^{115}Xe the π ef alignment is predicted to occur after, and be more gradual than, the ν EF alignment. Band 3 is interpreted in this work to be based on the $\nu g_{7/2}[413]5/2^+$ orbital.

Band 4 has not been previously identified therefore no configuration has been previously assigned to this band. There is a sharp backbend observed at $\sim 0.30 \text{ MeV}\hbar^{-1}$ and occurs over $\sim 0.05 \text{ MeV}\hbar^{-1}$ which is likely due to the ν EF alignment that is predicted to occur at $\sim 0.31 \text{ MeV}$. Following this backbend, the aligned angular momentum in this band continues to gradually increase with rotational frequency until around $0.35 \text{ MeV}\hbar^{-1}$. This could be the result of the π ef alignment which is predicted to occur at $\sim 0.44 \text{ MeV}\hbar^{-1}$ and be more gradual than the ν EF alignment. However, it could also be the result of the ν FG alignment which is predicted to occur at $\sim 0.45 \text{ MeV}\hbar^{-1}$. The aligned angular momentum in Band 4 is not observed above $\sim 0.46 \text{ MeV}\hbar^{-1}$. Therefore, it cannot be determined if any of the alignments predicted above this rotational frequency occur. The backbend observed in Band 4 follows a similar trend to that in Band 3 which suggests that these bands could be signature partners. Therefore, Band 4 also follows a similar trend to the alignment in this yrast band of ^{116}Xe . This is only the case for the low-lying excited states and as higher states are reached the

aligned angular momenta deviate from the trend in ^{116}Xe , shown in Panel (d) of Figure 7.6. In this work, Band 4 is interpreted to be the negative-signature partner to Band 3 and is proposed to have a configuration of B. This corresponds to Band 4 being based on the $\nu g_{7/2}[413]5/2^+$ orbital.

Chapter 8

Conclusion

In the $A \sim 110$ region of the nuclear chart, nuclei with $N = Z = 56$ are predicted to have maximum octupole correlations. As a result there is motivation to study excited states and hence determine the structure of the neutron-deficient nuclei with these nucleon numbers. In this work, an experiment was performed at Legnaro National Laboratory in order to search for excited states in ^{116}Ba ($Z = 56$, $N = 60$), using the $^{64}\text{Zn}(^{58}\text{Ni}, \alpha 2n)$ fusion-evaporation reaction. During the experiment, the prompt γ rays were detected using the Galileo detector array, the evaporated charged particles were detected using Euclides and the evaporated neutrons were detected using the Neutron Wall. The nucleus of interest is very neutron-deficient and for excited states to be populated one α particle and two neutrons must be evaporated from the compound nucleus. Analysis of the data from that experiment resulted in the identification of new γ -ray transitions in the $\alpha 2n$ -gated matrix however further investigation concluded that these transitions were not emitted from excited states in ^{116}Ba . The energy of the first 2^+ excited state in ^{116}Ba is expected to occur between 220-250 keV; this energy range was determined using systematics of the first 2^+ states in the known even-even barium isotopes. Gates were set on any transitions which had energies within this energy range. The resulting spectra were carefully studied and nuclei from which the γ rays were emitted were identified. Unfortunately, no transitions in ^{116}Ba were observed. The

detection efficiency of the Neutron Wall during the experiment was low and was measured to be around 1.5%. Consequently, the resulting spectra in the n- and 2n-gated matrices were produced with very few counts. Using the α -gated matrix only to search for ^{116}Ba was not possible as there were nuclei populated in the α reaction channels with much larger cross sections. Therefore, a higher neutron-detection efficiency would have been useful for reducing transitions from the more dominant nuclei, in the spectrum. The detection efficiency of the protons and α particles were lower than expected in the experiment with measured values of 28(4)% and 24(2)%, respectively. Due to the low particle-detection efficiencies, the particle-gated spectra were highly contaminated with transitions from neighbouring nuclei. Despite this, the detection of the evaporated particles allowed transitions from weakly-populated nuclei to be identified using channel selection techniques. Identifying excited states in ^{116}Ba could have been more likely in this experiment if higher particle-detection efficiencies could have been achieved.

In searching for transitions in ^{116}Ba , a number of unidentified transitions were observed. Following investigation using spectra gated on evaporated particles, these unidentified transitions were assigned to ^{115}Xe which was produced in the $\alpha 2\text{pn}$ evaporation channel. To assist in assigning these transitions to that nucleus, a data set from an experiment performed at Argonne National Laboratory was studied. That experiment involved the $^{58}\text{Ni}(^{64}\text{Zn})$ fusion-evaporation reaction. During the experiment, prompt γ rays were detected using the Gammasphere detector array, the evaporated charged particles were detected using the Microball and the mass of the recoiling nuclei were determined using the Fragment Mass Analyser. The detection efficiency of the protons and α particles were higher in that experiment with values of 83(1)% and 65(2)%, respectively. Particle-gated cubes were sorted and coincidence techniques were used to assist in determining the arrangement of the excited states from which the new transitions were emitted. The level scheme which was previously deduced for ^{115}Xe by Paul *et al.* has been extended [89]. The previously identified level scheme consisted of four bands and the γ -rays transitions in three of the bands have been observed in this work. However, the transitions in one of the bands have not been observed and it is proposed

here that the transitions have been misassigned from the neighbouring ^{114}I nucleus. The new transitions observed in this work were arranged into an additional band using energy, intensity and angular distribution measurements. The new band is observed up to spins of $43/2 \hbar$ and is linked to other bands in the original level scheme via four γ -ray transitions. The yrast band has also been tentatively extended to $51/2 \hbar$. Aligned angular momenta of the states were studied to assist in assigning configurations to each band in ^{115}Xe . The experimental alignment frequencies have been compared to results from theoretical predictions extracted from cranked shell model calculations and from systematics of neighbouring nuclei. On this basis, the bands have been proposed to be based on configurations of particles in the $\nu h_{11/2}$, $\pi h_{11/2}$, $\pi g_{7/2}$ and $\nu g_{7/2}$ orbitals. The use of n-gated spectra was important in the observation of the new transitions in this work despite of the low neutron-detection efficiency. Although the use of the Neutron Wall in the Galileo experiment was not helpful for identifying excited states in ^{116}Ba , it is unlikely that the new transitions in ^{115}Xe would have been identified without the use of neutron detectors.

Following this work, there are still no known excited states in ^{116}Ba and its structure remains unstudied experimentally. It would be useful to carry out another experiment to search for transitions in ^{116}Ba but using a more efficient neutron detector array. There is no other reaction with stable beams which can produce a more neutron-deficient cerium isotope than ^{122}Ce . Therefore, using the same reaction but with a neutron detector array with a higher 2n detection efficiency would be useful. An alternative to using neutron detectors could be to perform an experiment in which a recoil mass separator is used. A potential facility where this could be carried out is at the University of Jyväskylä in which EUROGAM III could be used together with the MARA recoil separator. There could also be the possibility to move away from stable beams and instead use radioactive beams in attempt to study this nucleus. Experiments like this could be carried out at facilities such as CERN using ISOLDE or at Legnaro National Laboratory using the new SPES radioactive beam facility. The search for excited states in ^{116}Ba should be continued in future work to investigate octupole correlations in the neutron-deficient barium isotopes. Future work could also involve the

search for excited states and octupole deformation in other nuclei in the $A < 120$ mass region, such as ^{114}Ba . One of the main goals of research in this mass region is to identify excited states in ^{112}Ba ($N = Z = 56$) and to investigate the prediction by Skalski that this nucleus will have maximum octupole correlations [8]. Strong octupole correlations in ^{112}Ba may lead to a band of states with alternating positive and negative parity, like those seen in the actinide region. Recently, the α decay of $^{108}\text{Xe} \rightarrow ^{104}\text{Te} \rightarrow ^{100}\text{Sn}$ was observed by Auranen *et al.* [105]. This is interesting for the future prospects of this work as it may be possible to identify ^{112}Ba via the $^{112}\text{Ba} \rightarrow ^{108}\text{Xe} \rightarrow ^{104}\text{Te} \rightarrow ^{100}\text{Sn}$ α decay chain, and subsequent to the identification of ^{112}Ba , it may be possible to identify excited states in that nucleus.

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Appendix A

A.1 Measured properties of ^{115}Xe transitions

Table A.1: Measured properties of the γ -ray transitions in ^{115}Xe . The columns are labelled with their contents. E_γ and I_γ give the energy in keV and relative intensity of the γ -ray, respectively. The intensities are relative to the 415-keV transition. The columns labelled I_i^π and I_f^π give the initial and final spins. The given multipolarities are inferred from the angular-distribution ratios R_θ . The spins and multipolarities are tentative. The band to which the transition is assigned to is given.

E_γ (keV)	I_γ	$I_i^\pi \rightarrow I_f^\pi$	R_θ	Multipolarity	Band
208.8(1)	3.3(3)	$\frac{33}{2}^+ \rightarrow \frac{31}{2}^+$	1.08(6) ¹	(M1)	2→4
210.4(1)		$\frac{7}{2}^+ \rightarrow \frac{5}{2}^+$	0.85(1)	M1/E2	4
221.3(2)		$(\frac{5}{2}^+) \rightarrow (\frac{5}{2}^+)$		(M1/E2)	3
350.4(3)		$(\frac{9}{2}^+) \rightarrow (\frac{5}{2}^+)$		(E2)	3
360.9(2)		$\frac{9}{2}^+ \rightarrow \frac{7}{2}^+$	0.89(7)	(M1)	3→4
374.2(1)	17(2)	$\frac{17}{2}^+ \rightarrow \frac{15}{2}^+$	0.73(9)	M1	3→4
415.2(2)		$\frac{15}{2}^- \rightarrow \frac{11}{2}^-$	1.32(3)	E2	1
543.4(3)		$\frac{11}{2}^+ \rightarrow \frac{7}{2}^+$	1.33(4)	E2	4

¹Based on the spins and parities this transition is expected to be an M1 transition however this measurement could have some contamination from ^{119}Cs

E_γ (keV)	I_γ	$I_i^\pi \rightarrow I_f^\pi$	R_θ	Multipolarity	Band
558.4(2)	9(1)	$(\frac{13}{2}^+) \rightarrow (\frac{9}{2}^+)$		(E2)	3
566.4(3)	17(2)	$(\frac{25}{2}^+) \rightarrow (\frac{21}{2}^+)$		(E2)	2
577.7(3)	23(3)	$(\frac{29}{2}^+) \rightarrow (\frac{25}{2}^+)$		(E2)	2
600.4(2)	5(1)	$(\frac{17}{2}^+) \rightarrow (\frac{13}{2}^+)$		(E2)	3
603.1(1)	87(10)	$\frac{15}{2}^+ \rightarrow \frac{11}{2}^+$	1.53(4)	E2	4
603.7(2)	8(1)	$(\frac{21}{2}^+) \rightarrow (\frac{17}{2}^+)$		(E2)	3
618.2(3)	69(8)	$(\frac{19}{2}^+) \rightarrow (\frac{15}{2}^+)$		(E2)	4
635.4(1)		$\frac{19}{2}^- \rightarrow \frac{15}{2}^-$	1.56(3)	E2	1
637.9(2)	60(7)	$\frac{23}{2}^+ \rightarrow \frac{19}{2}^+$	1.45(3)	E2	4
658.6(1)	50(6)	$\frac{27}{2}^+ \rightarrow \frac{23}{2}^+$	1.45(7)	E2	4
719.9(3)	19(3)	$(\frac{31}{2}^+) \rightarrow (\frac{27}{2}^+)$		(E2)	4
723.4(3)	15(3)	$(\frac{33}{2}^+) \rightarrow (\frac{29}{2}^+)$		(E2)	2
724.4(3)	16(3)	$(\frac{35}{2}^+) \rightarrow (\frac{31}{2}^+)$		(E2)	4
768.3(1)	100(13)	$\frac{23}{2}^- \rightarrow \frac{19}{2}^-$	1.32(7)	E2	1
835.1(2)	14(2)	$(\frac{39}{2}^+) \rightarrow (\frac{35}{2}^+)$		(E2)	4
837.6(2)	26(4)	$(\frac{25}{2}^+) \rightarrow (\frac{23}{2}^-)$		(E1)	2→1
854.2(3)	69(9)	$\frac{27}{2}^- \rightarrow \frac{23}{2}^-$	1.61(4)	E2	1
892.3(4)		$(\frac{37}{2}^+) \rightarrow (\frac{33}{2}^+)$		(E2)	2
920.0(1)	52(7)	$(\frac{31}{2}^-) \rightarrow (\frac{27}{2}^-)$		(E2)	1
938.8(2)	6(1)	$(\frac{43}{2}^+) \rightarrow (\frac{39}{2}^+)$		(E2)	4
941.7(3)	25(4)	$(\frac{39}{2}^-) \rightarrow (\frac{35}{2}^-)$		(E2)	1
953.4(1)	41(6)	$(\frac{35}{2}^-) \rightarrow (\frac{31}{2}^-)$		(E2)	1
1021.5(4)		$(\frac{41}{2}^+) \rightarrow (\frac{37}{2}^+)$		(E2)	2
1038.2(3)		$(\frac{21}{2}^+) \rightarrow (\frac{19}{2}^-)$		(E1)	2→1

Appendix B

B.1 TRS deformations

The following figures are extracted from the TRS calculations for ^{115}Xe as discussed in Section 7.1. The figures show TRS plots for the configurations of A, B, C, D, E, F, G and H. The four-lowest steps in rotational frequency, with $\omega = 0, 0.064, 0.128$ and $0.191 \text{ MeV}\hbar^{-1}$, are shown for each configuration. For each step in rotational frequency the deformation parameters are given.

Figure B.1: The output of the TRS calculations for the odd neutron in ¹¹⁵Xe with configuration A.

Figure B.2: The output of the TRS calculations for the odd neutron in ¹¹⁵Xe with configuration B.

Figure B.3: The output of the TRS calculations for the odd neutron in ¹¹⁵Xe with configuration C.

Figure B.4: The output of the TRS calculations for the odd neutron in ¹¹⁵Xe with configuration D.

Figure B.5: The output of the TRS calculations for the odd neutron in ¹¹⁵Xe with configuration E.

Figure B.6: The output of the TRS calculations for the odd neutron in ^{115}Xe with configuration F.

Figure B.7: The output of the TRS calculations for the odd neutron in ¹¹⁵Xe with configuration G.

Figure B.8: The output of the TRS calculations for the odd neutron in ¹¹⁵Xe with configuration H.